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Achieving sustainable development and debt sustainability in developing countries: To what extent do debt-for-nature swaps matter?

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Abstract

This paper assesses the impact of debt-for-nature swaps on sustainable development in developing countries, using entropy balancing on a large sample of 127 countries from 1990 to 2020. The findings indicate that debt-for-nature swaps have a positive and statistically significant effect on sustainable development, operating through several key channels: public debt reduction, increased public investment, lower CO₂ emissions, and improved human development. The additional results found in this paper show that if the treated countries had not benefited from debt-for-nature swaps, their sustainable development index would have decreased by 11%. At the same time, if untreated countries had benefited from debt-for-nature swaps, their Sustainable Development Index would have increased by around 2%. The analysis also reveals a non-linear relationship between the size of debt-for-nature swaps and the sustainable development index, with an optimal threshold estimated at 42% of the public debt level, beyond which diminishing returns are observed. These results suggest that debt-for-nature swaps can serve as an effective financing tool for sustainable development, provided that they are appropriately designed. From a policy perspective, expanding debt-for-nature swap programs requires broadening eligibility criteria, strengthening transparency and governance of environmental funds, and more systematically integrating climate objectives into multilateral debt relief mechanisms. Enhanced coordination between public and private creditors, as well as environmental organizations, is also crucial to ensure that debt-for-nature swaps support the ecological transition effectively in the most vulnerable countries.

Keywords: • Debt swap operation • Debt relief debt swap • Debt conversion
• Sustainable development • Developing countries

JEL Codes: E51, Q43, Q54, Q56

1 Introduction

The sovereign debt crisis in developing countries after COVID-19 has strained the availability of financial resources for sustainable development and risks exacerbating the funding gap for nature (Barbier, 2022), while efforts to provide jobs and job security have led to stimulus policies that have potentially resulted in economic growth without regard to negative environmental consequences (Fodha and Seegmuller, 2014). Indeed, these corollaries of COVID-19, combined with the Russo-Ukrainian crisis and possible evaluations of sovereign debt restructuring (ECA, 2022; AfDB, 2022; Essers et al., 2021), have provided a window of opportunity to reassess development models (Elliott et al., 2020; Oldekop et al., 2020).

To achieve sustainable development, developing countries, international institutions, NGOs, etc., are committed to finding a solution to the sovereign debt crisis, to enable indebted countries to have budgetary leeway for the climate. The resolution of the sovereign debt crisis is more crucial than ever to achieving sustainable development goals, because unsustainable debt reduces fiscal space and weakens the government’s capacity to tackle climate change (Boly et al., 2022; Van and Azomahou, 2007). In this regard, debt relief programs have been initiated. Despite efforts made, these programs have not succeeded in keeping debt levels at a sustainable level for a long time, particularly in times of crisis. At the same time, these programs have shown their limitations in terms of climate financing. For instance, the G20 Debt Service Suspension Initiative (DSSI) and the Common Framework (World Bank, 2021)¹ temporarily suspended debt service payments between May 2020 and December 2021 for up to 73 eligible countries whose debt levels had become unsustainable during the COVID-19 crisis. It should be noted that DSSI had only been initiated once and had only provided \$12.9 billion in aid to 48 countries, while the Common Framework had not led to any significant debt reorganization by May 2023, with only four countries having requested treatment under it (Alkhareif and Moulin, 2023)². In addition, debt reduction has been adopted through the joint initiative of the International Monetary Fund-World Bank Heavily Indebted Poor Countries and the Multilateral Debt Reduction Initiative. However, the higher levels of debt reduction granted to eligible countries by these programs have not been linked to the protection of environmental and biodiversity (Sommer et al., 2020). This highlights the challenges of these approaches as a tool for debt reduction and sustainable growth.

The fundamental question for developing countries is to find a financing model capable of fulfilling two major functions, i.e. providing countries with budgetary resources by reducing public debt and increasing their capacity to combat climate change (Raworth; 2012; 2017). The debt-for-nature swaps (DNS) initiative, via the cancellation of debt

¹<https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/debt/brief/covid-19-debt-service-suspension-initiative>.

²https://findevlab.org/news_and_event/what-the-chad-debt-deal-means/.

services for conservation, could therefore be an effective way of achieving these dual objectives. Basically, the central idea of a debt-for-nature swap involves reducing the debt of a low- or middle-income country in exchange for that country's investment in environmental conservation and protection (Paul et al., 2023; AfDB, 2022; d Chamon et al., 2022; Essers et al., 2021; Simmons et al., 2021; Volz et al., 2021; Picolotti et al., 2020; Sommer et al., 2020; Steele and Patel, 2020; Sheikh, 2018; Hamlin, 1989; Hansen, 1989).

Historically, DNS was initially developed in the 1980s to address this dual environmental and sovereign debt problem by exchanging sovereign debt for conservation or restoration of nature (Nedopil et al., 2024). Indeed, this debt relief program has proven effective in countries such as the Seychelles, which adopted the program in 2015, and Belize in 2021 (d Chamon et al., 2022). This has surpassed the appeal of some to adopt the policy³. DNS has restructured around 3 billion dollars (Jones and Campos, 2023); with a single DNS exchange debt worth up to 1.6% of national GDP since 2015 after its drastic fall in the 1990s due to the HIPC program. According to Sommer et al. (2020), in total, US-led debt-for-nature swaps have canceled around \$1.8 billion in favor of 21 low- and middle-income countries. The swaps generated \$400 million for conservation.

However, the effectiveness of DNS is rather ambiguous in the literature. For instance, Jones and Campos (2023) based on the recent case of Ecuador and the Maldives illustrate the potential of DNS to provide a fund mobilization solution for conservation, resolving the debt crisis, and also enabling national credit ratings to revive the economy. These results were confirmed by Heller (2005). In addition, Gockel and Gray (2011) evaluated two projects funded by a US debt-for-nature swap signed in 2002 that canceled \$14 million of Peruvian debt and generated \$10 million for conservation. The authors conclude from a survey of 57 villagers living near the reserve and interviews with non-governmental organization staff that the first project effectively improved species conservation and socioeconomic well being, and the second succeeded in improving the capacity of local people to manage forest resources, while improving the capacity of national non-governmental organizations to manage the projects described above. Using a two-stage instrumental variable regression model to analyze a sample of 85 low- and middle-income countries from 2001 to 2014, Sommer et al. (2020) find that higher amounts of debt reduction and higher amounts of conservation funds generated as a result of such swaps are associated with lower rates of forest loss. However, Kraemer and Hartmann (1993) analyzed cross-national data for 34 low- and middle-income countries using ordinary least squares regression and found no relationship between participation in a debt-for-nature swap and forest loss. Even the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund (IMF), two of the largest creditors in developing countries, had evaluated the inclusion of DNS to restructure their debt by May 2021 (Shalal, 2021). Although this was seen as a potentially powerful solution for overall debt sustainability (Georgieva and Thakoor, 2022), progress stalled due to uncertainties about DNS scalability (Shalal, 2022). Our research contributes

³This countries are Barbados in 2022, Ecuador and Gabon in 2023 (see Nedopil et al., 2024).

to this fascinating debate by assessing the effectiveness of DNS in developing countries. Based on the study by [Nedopil and Sun \(2025\)](#), we reveal several limitations of previous studies on debt-for-nature swap. First, existing studies are descriptive analyses and lack a clear method to analyze the effectiveness of DNS on macroeconomic or environmental variables (see, for example, [Paul et al., 2023](#); [Sheikh, 2018](#); [Hansen, 1989](#)). Second, the analyses carried out have focused on national cases (see, for example, [Essers et al., 2021](#); [Cassimon et al., 2011](#), for a discussion) or a special case of debt-for-nature swaps from the United Nations (see, e.g. [Sommer et al., 2020](#)), thus limiting their external validity. Third, most existing studies focus on assessing the effectiveness of DNS in reducing forest cover (see [Sommer et al., 2020](#); [Sheikh, 2018](#)). None of these studies analyzes the effect of DNS on a variable that takes into account both human development and environmental sustainability.

In this context, the aim of the paper is to fill this gap in the economic literature by analyzing the impact of DNS on ecological efficiency from an empirical perspective to enrich the political debate on development sustainability and debt relief programs. To achieve this, we use the ecological efficiency index constructed by [Hickel \(2020\)](#). This index takes into account all the factors involved in improving human development and measuring ecological impact ([Hickel, 2020](#)). In fact, the Sustainable Development Index (SDI) corrects the Human Development Index (HDI), which has long been criticized for not taking ecological sustainability into account. Our intuition is that DNS on the budgetary level, by enlarging the fiscal space of beneficiary countries via debt relief, enables them to invest in numerous development projects which create jobs and wealth, boosting the level of global income. In the environmental plan, the DNS obliges countries to invest in the conservation and protection of biodiversity, allowing them to achieve ecological efficiency. These combined effects will have a positive impact on the Sustainable Development Index.

Based on DNS transmission mechanisms for sustainable development, the resulting hypotheses are as follows: *(H1) DNS reduce environmental degradation (deforestation) and CO2 emissions by improving ecological efficiency indicators; (H2) DNS increase the sustainable development index by reducing debt burden, increasing economic growth, and improving well-being.*

To empirically test these main hypotheses, we use the entropy-balancing method, which deals with the self-selection bias associated with DNS adoption. We found that benefiting from debt-for-nature significantly increases sustainable development in developing countries. This study contributes to the literature in several ways. Firstly, it sheds new light on the important role of DNS in achieving sustainable development. It provides empirical evidence in response to the pessimistic view held by some international institutions that DNS is an effective instrument for achieving sustainable development and should therefore be extended to several debtor countries. Secondly, to our knowledge, this study is the first to empirically and rigorously evaluate the effectiveness of DNS in achieving

sustainable development by addressing the problem of self-selection, as suggested by [Bare et al. \(2015\)](#). In addition, the distinction between the two main types of DNS, namely bilateral debt-for-nature and multi-party debt-for-nature swaps, is crucial for assessing the scope of the policy. Finally, we controlled for time- and country-fixed effects as recommended by [Sommer et al. \(2020\)](#), sensitivity to the time elapsed since DNS adoption, and several other governance indicators. The main results support the conclusion that DNS is an effective debt relief program to achieve sustainable development.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section [2](#) examines the effectiveness of DNS as an instrument to reduce debt burdens and improve environmental quality. Then, Section [3](#) describes the empirical methodology. Section [4](#) presents the data used in this study, while the main results are presented in Section [5](#). Section [6](#) examines the sensitivity of these results, while Section [7](#) explores the heterogeneity tests. Section [8](#) discusses the channels through which DNS affects sustainable development. Finally, Section [9](#) concludes the study and presents the policy recommendations from the results.

2 Investigating the effectiveness of debt-for-nature swaps as a debt and nature sustainability tools.

Given that DNS have been designed to achieve two main objectives, namely debt and environmental sustainability, we examine in this section the theoretical and empirical debates on its effectiveness in promoting debt and environmental sustainability.

2.1 *On the fiscal space side*

The economic literature seems to be pessimistic about the effectiveness of DNS in creating fiscal space for the debtor country due to the size of the cancelled debt. For instance, [Cassimon et al. \(2011\)](#) evaluated the effectiveness of the largest bilateral debt-for-nature swap carried out by the United States with Indonesia in 2011. To achieve this, the authors analyzed exchange documents and statistical data to determine how it performed in the face of several identified limitations of these transactions. The authors determined that Indonesia had cancelled approximately \$22 million in debt owed to the United States. However, the debt-for-nature swap did not generate any additional budgetary space in the Indonesian budget, as the payments were redirected to a conservation fund ([Cassimon et al., 2011](#)). At the same time, the authors estimate that the amount of debt cancelled thanks to this debt-for-nature swap represented only a fraction of Indonesia's outstanding debt, making it unlikely that the amount of debt cancelled would have had a considerable effect on the country's fiscal space. Similarly, although the US debt-for-nature swap with the Peruvian government cancelled \$14.3 million and generated \$10 million for conservation, it did not generate any budgetary space for the country ([Gockel and Gray, 2011](#)). Moreover, since the nominal value of debt-for-nature transactions generally represents an overestimate of both the benefit to the debtor and the cost to the creditor ([Cassimon et al., 2011](#)), an exchange may provide fewer resources than, say, direct budget support ([Birdsall et al., 2003](#); [Bulow and Rogoff, 1991](#)). In fact, the savings from debt relief are only realized gradually, usually over several years or even decades, depending on the contractual repayment terms and timing of the underlying debt ([Cassimon et al., 2011](#)). In this respect, the declared nominal value of debt cancelled under a swap is not necessarily a reliable measure of the increase in resources available to the debtor country ([Cassimon et al., 2011](#)). According to [Chamon et al. \(2022\)](#), despite the frequency of debt swaps, the total volume of debt relief they have generated has remained modest. In fact, as explained above, the main reason for this is the small size of the transactions: most debt swaps are in the double-digit million US dollar range; the largest swap to date took place in 1992 between Poland and a group of creditors, for a total value of \$580 million. Another reason is that debt swaps generally replace an old debt with a new one. This leads [Cassimon et al. \(2011\)](#) to say that genuine fiscal space is only created when there is a positive difference between the debt service payments cancelled under the debt swap

and the counterpart payments that replace them. Going a step further, [Cassimon et al. \(2011\)](#) point the finger at the structuring of debt-for-nature swaps. For the authors, a poorly structured debt-for-nature swap, in which annual domestic counterpart payments take place before debt relief savings are realized, can therefore worsen rather than improve the government's fiscal position, depending on the NPV of debt service payments and domestic counterpart payments. The idea defended by these authors is that debt relief must reach a critical mass and be granted in a harmonized manner if it is to have any chance of freeing a country from its debt burden and the ensuing economic impasse. However, debt-for-nature swaps have always been piecemeal interventions whose scale, in relation to the overall debt stock of recipient countries, is deemed insufficient to have a significant impact (see also, [Hamlin, 1989](#); [Patterson, 1990](#); [Hansen, 1989](#); [Thapa, 1998](#)).

The above suggests that unnatural debt swaps, which appear generous at first glance, can only lead to minor hard currency gains for the recipient country. However, debt-for-nature swaps are often seen as generating additional fiscal space ([Heller, 2005](#)) in the recipient country's budget, which it can spend without jeopardizing the stability of its fiscal and macroeconomic situation.

Indeed, the pre-adoption conditions of debt-for-nature swaps can lead to an improvement in macroeconomic and institutional indicators, generating fiscal space for the beneficiary country. In fact, there are various economic, political and environmental conditions that a nation must meet to participate in an unnatural bilateral debt swap with the United States ([Sheikh, 2016](#)). In terms of economic requirements, a debtor government must have reached debt service thresholds and demonstrate progress in implementing reforms involving an International Monetary Fund (IMF) or World Bank (WB) structural adjustment agreement (see [UNCBD, 2001](#)). This may lead to the adoption of certain fiscal reforms, such as budgetary rules to prevent possible fiscal debauchery and create fiscal space for the country ([Sawadogo, 2020](#)). In the political sphere, a debtor nation must have a democratically elected government and demonstrate its commitment to guaranteeing human rights ([UNCBD, 2001](#)). This will undoubtedly improve institutional indicators and reinforce the effectiveness of budget reforms in dissuading the government from discretionary spending (see [Nerlich and Heinrich Reuter, 2015](#)). In addition, given that DNS offers the possibility of ongoing interest payments from the debtor government on the remaining debt to the environmental trust fund, this reduces moral hazard, i.e. the debtor country taking unjustified future risk and re-exposing itself to debt obligations due to its previous experience of debt cancellation ([Nedopil et al., 2024](#)). DNS also guarantees local benefits from national investments ([Ferry, 2019](#)), creating jobs for the people living on the periphery. This, in turn, broadens the government's tax base.

Although there is some controversy in the literature about the effectiveness of DNS in generating fiscal space, it must be acknowledged that DNS have helped to reduce the debtor country's stock of debt for the preservation of the environment ([UNDP, 2017](#)). For instance, the first debt-for-nature agreement signed in 1987 between Bolivia and

Conservation International (CI) enabled the purchase of US \$650,000 of Bolivia's foreign debt on the secondary market at a reduced price of US \$100,000 (see [Nedopil et al., 2024](#)). In addition, the value of debt restructured under the DNS agreements exceeded US \$2.6 billion, resulting in approximately US \$1.2 billion in transfers to conservation projects between 1987-2015 ([UNDP, 2017](#)). DNS in Seychelles represented in 2018 more than 1.5% of GDP ([UNCBD, 2001](#)) and DNS increased the amount of debt exchanged, from several million per exchange in the 1980s to 1.6 billion US dollars in a single exchange in 2023 ([Jones and Campos, 2023](#)).

2.2 On the environmental sustainability side

On the environmental side, it should be noted that most studies have only assessed the relationship between DNS and deforestation, and related literature shows that the effectiveness of DNS is ambiguous. For instance, [Sheikh \(2010\)](#) argues that debt-for-nature swaps are seen as a way of raising funds to reduce environmental degradation while mitigating debtor countries' desperate search for hard currency. Similarly, [Nedopil et al. \(2024\)](#) evaluated the effectiveness of DNS, focusing on the nature, amount and beneficiary. They constructed a dataset on biodiversity conservation and debt restructuring in 67 countries threatened by sovereign debt overhang and holding over 22% of the world's priority biodiversity areas, 82.96% of which are unprotected. Using conservative cost estimates, the authors show that for 35 of the 67 countries, 100% of unprotected biodiversity priority areas could be protected for a fraction of the debt; for the remaining countries, application of DNS would protect 11-13% of currently unprotected biodiversity priority areas. [Shandra et al. \(2011\)](#) are interested in the effectiveness of DNS, particularly commercial DNS on forest loss. Using transnational models of forest loss for the period 1990-2005, the authors find that poor countries that implement such exchanges tend to have lower deforestation rates than poor countries that do not. In addition, poor countries with higher levels of international non-governmental organizations have lower rates of forest loss.

In the same veins, [Sommer et al. \(2020\)](#) looked at the effectiveness of debt-for-nature swaps in promoting environmental protection, more specifically US bilateral debt-for-nature swaps. Using a two-stage instrumental variable regression model to analyse a sample of 85 low- and middle-income countries from 2001 to 2014, the authors find that higher amounts of debt reduction and higher amounts of conservation funds generated as a result of such swaps are associated with lower rates of forest loss. [Picolotti et al. \(2020\)](#) call for the extension of debt swaps as a means of helping countries build climate resilience and support pandemic recovery. [Steele and Patel \(2020\)](#) argue for debt swaps in favor of spending programs rather than projects, i.e. spending related to climate resilience, adaptation and biodiversity protection, which give recipient governments flexibility in the use of funds. [Volz et al. \(2021\)](#) propose swapping existing debt for "recovery bonds" linking payment terms to the fulfillment of policy and spending commitments set out in

a green and inclusive recovery strategy developed by debtor governments in consultation with civil society, creditors, international financial institutions (IFIs) and UN agencies.

Some studies suggest that DNS has not reduced deforestation. For instance, using OLS regressions, [Kraemer and Hartmann \(1993\)](#) found no relationship between participation in a debt-for-nature swap and forest loss in 34 countries. [Mak Arvin and Lew \(2009\)](#) find that higher levels of bilateral conservation aid actually correspond to increased, not decreased, forest loss. For [Bryant and Bailey \(1997\)](#), the agroforestry project carried out in Ecuador as part of a debt-for-nature swap failed shortly after it started because members could not agree among themselves how much time each person should allocate to the project. [Livernash and Paden \(1992\)](#) think that debt-for-nature swaps may have no impact on deforestation because they are small-scale operations.

By assessing the effectiveness of DNS in protecting the environment and by extension well-being, [Bryant and Bailey \(1997\)](#) argue that conservation projects funded by debt-for-nature swaps do not assist enough people in a large enough geographical area to have a meaningful impact on forest loss. This is also in line with [Bare et al. \(2015\)](#), who found in a sample of sub-Saharan African countries that programs such as DNS that create protected areas contribute to the displacement of local populations where the project is implemented, who then leave to clear forests elsewhere.

In summary, based on the discussions above, it's clearly that there is a debate regarding the efficacy of debt-for-nature swaps in decreasing forest loss. Specifically, the discussion of these potential limitations suggests that swaps may be ineffective in part because they are small scale ([Essers et al., 2021](#); [d Chamon et al., 2022](#); [Livernash and Paden, 1992](#)), ineffective management ([Watson et al., 2014](#)), limited in geographical scope ([Jakobeit, 1996](#)), or conducted without due regard for livelihoods of people ([Bryant and Bailey, 1997](#); [Gockel and Gray, 2011](#)). They may also be less effective in nations with weak property laws, high levels of repression, or high levels of corruption ([Shandra et al., 2011](#)).

However, these studies may produce counter-intuitive results by not addressing donor selection bias, examining a single geographic region or being based on descriptive analyses. For instance, [Kraemer and Hartmann \(1993\)](#) and [Shandra et al. \(2011\)](#) use the OLS method, which obviously does not control for selection bias. A more advanced impact evaluation method would have compared DNS and non-DNS individuals on the basis of similar characteristics. Indeed, it's not surprising that [Kraemer and Hartmann \(1993\)](#) found no significant effect of DNS. Firstly, their empirical results are based on a very small time span ($t=1$, $N=8;16;34$). A wider time frame would have captured the effect over time and over the long term, since according to [Jones and Campos \(2023\)](#) DNS increase in amount over time. Secondly, their results suffer from an endogeneity problem. Ignoring this problem leads to biased regression coefficients or ineffective statistical significance tests (see [Sommer et al., 2020](#)). Regarding the study of [Sommer et al. \(2020\)](#), the endogeneity problem is addressed, but suffers from a lack of data availability on several time points of the forest loss variable. Moreover, this study says nothing about DNS and

non-DNS observations, so that we can have a clear idea of the post-treatment period and the pre-treatment period. Even if the study retains all its quality, a weighting between DNS and non-DNS individuals to obtain a certain balance between pre-treatment and post-treatment periods would have enabled us to better identify the impact of DNS.

Following the logic of [Hermanrud and de Soysa \(2017\)](#), we postulate that it's important to use an appropriate statistical method that takes into account potential problems arising from donor selection bias. Consequently, this study uses a sophisticated impact evaluation approach that takes into account the problem of selection bias and compares treated and untreated individuals on the basis of a number of observable characteristics.

3 Methodology

The conviction that debt relief for environmental quality and the fight against climate change will free up budgetary space and enable climate financing to achieve sustainable development goals is what primarily motivates initiatives such as debt-for-nature swaps. Our objective is to analyze the causal effect of adopting debt-for-nature swaps on sustainable development measured by the ecological efficiency of human development. To do so, the simplest, often dubbed *naive approach* is to examine the impact of DNS on sustainable development by including in the sustainable development equation a dummy variable equal to 1 if the country has adopted DNS and to estimate the equation using ordinary least squares (OLS). This approach followed by [Shandra et al. \(2011\)](#) and [Kraemer and Hartmann \(1993\)](#) suffers, however, from a fundamental flaw. It assumes *de facto* that the DNS dummy variable is exogenous or equivalently that the decision to adopt DNS is random. If one takes seriously the work of [Hermanrud and de Soysa \(2017\)](#) and [Bare et al. \(2015\)](#), such an assumption is hardly tenable. Indeed, these authors provide evidence suggesting that the self-selection process of adopting DNS is endogenous rather than random, and depends among others upon a number of observable characteristics as discussed earlier. The literature on DNS also provides ample evidence of country self-selection based on observable characteristics (see our discussion in subsection 2.2 that refers to [Livernash and Paden, 1992](#); [Watson et al., 2014](#); [Jakobeit, 1996](#); [Bryant and Bailey, 1997](#); [Shandra et al., 2011](#); [Essers et al., 2021](#)). In other words, DNS-countries have systematically different characteristics from non-DNS countries, and may have decided to adopt based on their own expected benefits. Unobservable characteristics of countries may also affect both the decision to adopt DNS and sustainable development, resulting in biased estimates of the effect of adopting DNS on sustainable development. Practically, this implies that the so-called *naive* treatment of DNS dummy as an exogenous variable in an OLS estimation as in [Shandra et al. \(2011\)](#) is likely to be flawed (see [Guo and Fraser, 2014](#) for a non-technical exposition of the sample selection problem).

Since there are good reasons to suspect the presence of non-random (endogenous) self-selection, the selection process must be modeled explicitly otherwise the impact of

DNS implementation is likely to be biased. Various methods have been developed to correct selection bias by modeling explicitly the endogenous treatment (here the decision of adopting DNS) in addition to the effect of the treatment on sustainable development index. In this paper, we use a treatment effects model, which estimates simultaneously the decision to adopt DNS and sustainable development which is called in literature entropy balancing method developed by [Hainmueller \(2012\)](#). Entropy balancing approach has many advantages and is widely used in economic literature. For instance, [Balima and Sy \(2021\)](#) used it to examine the role of IMF-supported programs in reducing the likelihood of subsequent sovereign defaults in borrowing countries, [Apeti and Edoh \(2023\)](#) has used it to assess the impact of mobile money on tax revenue mobilization, [Apeti \(2023\)](#) also used it to evaluate the effect of mobile money adoption on household consumption volatility, [Kinda and Thiombiano \(2024\)](#) have used to examine the implementing the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative (EITI) standard on deforestation in natural resource-rich developing countries, and [Jacolin et al. \(2021\)](#) used it to investigate the impact of mobile financial services in particular, mobile money, mobile credit, and savings on the informal sector. The entropy method is a non-parametric model that allows us to obtain the treatment effect on treated individuals (ATT). Thus, ATT's equation is as follows:

$$ATT = E[(Y_{(1)}|DNS=1, X = 1)] - E[Y_0|DNS=1, X = 1] \quad (1)$$

where $Y_{i(.)}$ is the outcome variable measuring the ecological efficiency of human development. DNS_i indicates whether the observation unit is subject to debt-for-nature swaps adoption ($DNS_i = 1$) or not ($DNS_i = 0$). $E[(Y_{i(1)}|DNS_i=1)]$ is the ecological efficiency of human development level during the debt-for-nature swaps adoption period, $E[(Y_{i0}|DNS_i=1)]$ is the counterfactual result for countries that had adopted debt-for-nature swaps, i.e. the ecological efficiency of human development in countries that had adopted debt-for-nature swaps if they had not.

The issue is that $E[Y(0)|DNS = 1]$ is not observable due to the non-random nature of DNS adoption. If this were the case, the ATT could easily be identified by comparing the ecological efficiency of human development in DNS countries with non-DNS countries. Identifying ATT then requires a good proxy for $E[Y(0)|DNS = 1]$. To do so, we match DNS units with non-DNS units (after purging for some specific factors) that are as close as possible on observable characteristics that meet two criteria: correlated with DNS adoption and ecological efficiency of human development. Under the condition that the non-DNS units are fairly close to the DNS units, any difference in ecological efficiency of human development is attributable to DNS adoption. Based on these details, we can rewrite Eq 1 as follows:

$$ATT = E[(Y_{(1)}|DNS=1, X = x)] - E[Y_0|DNS=1, X = x] \quad (2)$$

where $X = x$ is a vector of observable covariates that may affect both the decision to adopt DNS and the ecological efficiency of human development, $E[Y(1)|DNS = 1, X = x]$

is the ecological efficiency of human development of DNS units, and $E[Y(0)|DNS = 0, X = x]$ is the expected ecological efficiency of human development for the synthetic control units. Entropy balancing is a two-step estimation method. First, the weights assigned to the control units (in this case, the non-DNS countries) are calculated in the entropy balancing. Following [Neuenkirch and Neumeier \(2016\)](#), we choose balance constraints that impose equal covariates means between the treatment and control groups. In doing so, we want to ensure that the control group, on average, has non-treatment units that are as similar as possible to the treated units. The second uses the weights from the first step in a regression analysis where sustainable development is the dependent variable. In the second step, we control for the covariates employed in the first step. This is equivalent to including control variables in a randomized experiment and increases estimation efficiency. In addition, time— and country-specific effects are included in the second step to respectively account for time—specific effects such as the debt crisis, debt restructuring, climate vulnerability and country-specific heterogeneity arising from, for instance, differences with regard to political, economic, institutional environments, and climate change vulnerability. Thus, the average difference in ecological efficiency of human development between countries with DNS and the "*closest*" non-DNS countries should be explained by the DNS adoption.

Indeed, the advantage offered by the entropy balancing method of controlling for country and time fixed effects allows us to rigorously address one of the limitations of the study by [Sommer et al. \(2020\)](#), who felt that future DNS research should incorporate country and time-specific fixed effects into their regression models. This would enable stricter control of the invariant characteristics of nations that can affect the outcome variable, and could further prevent potential endogeneity problems (see [Wooldridge, 1996](#)). In addition, and as an advantage, entropy balancing allows us to identify the effect of DNS by comparing countries (or units) where DNS is present and others where it is not, which are similar in terms of observable characteristics, while taking care to account for country- and time-specific effects. By combining both a matching and a regression approach, this method offers some further advantages over several impact estimation methods such as propensity score matching, Diff-in-Diff, and coarsened exact matching as reported by [Neuenkirch and Neumeier \(2016\)](#). A particularly important advantage as mentioned above, is that entropy balancing is non-parametric in the sense that there is no need to specify an empirical model for the outcome variable or selection into treatment. Consequently, potential types of misspecification, such as those concerning the functional form of the empirical model, which are likely to lead to biased estimates, are excluded. In addition, unlike regression-based analyses, entropy balancing based estimates of treatment effects do not suffer from multicollinearity, as the reweighting scheme orthogonalizes the covariates with respect to the treatment indicator. Unlike the above—mentioned matching methods, entropy balancing guarantees a high degree of covariate balance between treatment and control groups, even in the case of small sample sizes. In fact, with the "conventional"

matching methods we cited above, each treated unit— in the simplest case— is matched with the untreated unit that is closest in terms of metric balancing score. As a result, the control group consists only of a subset of untreated units (Hainmueller, 2012). In other words, with conventional matching methods, each untreated unit is assigned a weight equal to 0, in the event that it does not represent the best match for a treated unit, or equal to 1, in the event that it represents the best match for a treated unit. However, when the number of untreated units is limited and the number of pre-treatment characteristics is high, this procedure does not guarantee a sufficient balance of pre-treatment characteristics between treatment and control groups. This is a serious problem, as poor covariate balance can lead to biased estimates of the treatment effect. In contrast, with entropy balancing, the vector of weights assigned to units not exposed to treatment can contain any non-negative value. Thus, a synthetic control group is designed to represent a virtually perfect image of the treatment group.

Finally, compared with conventional matching where control units are either eliminated or matched, entropy balancing uses more flexible reweighting schemes. It reweights units with the aim of achieving a balance between processed and unprocessed units, while keeping weights as close as possible to base weights to avoid loss of information. By combining a reweighting system with regression analysis, entropy balancing allows us to properly handle the panel structure of our data to account for potential unobserved heterogeneity between countries that have never adopted DNS and those that have, given that the economic, political and climatic conditions of these two groups of countries may differ beyond the set of covariates used in the entropy balancing approach.

4 Data and descriptive statistics

4.1 Data

To assess the effect of debt-for-nature swaps, we use an annual panel of 127 developing countries from 1990-2020. The choice of this sample is dictated by the availability of data and also by the fact that the adoption of debt-for-nature swaps is specific to developing countries (reduced fiscal space and very vulnerable to climate change). In other words, no developed country has adopted this policy to date (see Shandra et al., 2011).

Treatment variable. The treatment variable used in this paper is DNS, which is participation in a country’s debt-for-nature swap. In line with previous studies (AfDB, 2022; d Chamon et al., 2022; Picolotti et al., 2020; Sommer et al., 2020; Sheikh, 2018; Shandra et al., 2011), we measure the adoption of debt-for-nature swaps by a dummy variable, taking 1 if a country i at date t adopts debt-for-nature swaps, and 0 elsewhere. Over the study period, 95 out of 127 countries have never adopted debt-for-nature swaps, and the remaining 32 countries adopted it. In addition, note that no country has adopted debt-for-nature swaps before the sample of analysis. How debt-for-nature swaps can affect

the economy and achieve sustainable development is a matter of debate. For example, proponents of the swap, particularly those from the "World Polity" school of thought, assume that countries that have participated in a debt-for-nature swap should have lower deforestation rates. However, skeptics argue that debt-for-nature swaps should have no impact on forest loss.

Outcome variable. Our outcome variable is sustainable development index. The sustainable development index (SDI) measures the ecological efficiency of human development, recognizing that development must be achieved within planetary boundaries.⁴ In fact, this variable was constructed by [Hickel \(2020\)](#) to address the limits of the Human Development Index (HDI) in terms of ecological realities. HDI was originally designed to take account of countries' progress not only in terms of economic expansion, but also in terms of key social outcomes ([PNUD, 1992](#)). It is currently calculated as the geometric mean of three indicators: life expectancy at birth; education (the average of average years of schooling and expected years of schooling); and income (GNI per capita, PPP), which is placed on a natural logarithmic scale ([Hickel, 2020](#)). In this formula, it's clear to see that there are no indicators of ecological sustainability. This is surprising given the growing crisis of climate change and ecological degradation.

Indeed, some authors have attempted to address these ecological limitations of HDI (see [Pelenc et al., 2016](#); [Neuenkirch and Neumeier, 2016](#); [Sagar and Najam, 1998](#)). For instance, [Biggeri and Mauro \(2018\)](#) have recently developed an alternative index that incorporates not only an ecological indicator (CO2 emissions) but also an additional social indicator, freedom (defined as political rights and civil liberties). [Togtokh and Gaffney \(2010\)](#) included an index of CO2 emissions per capita in a geometric mean alongside the three original HDI indicators to integrate environmental dimensions. [Türe \(2013\)](#) by simplifying, divides the HDI by the "ecological footprint", which takes into account not only carbon emissions but also the biocapacity of cropland, grazing land, forests and fisheries. However, and according to [Hickel \(2020\)](#), the attempts made to date all suffer from notable weaknesses that make them ultimately unsuitable for two reasons. Firstly, for the author, most of the alternatives described above are indicators of weak sustainability, insofar as they allow compromises between development and ecology.⁵ Secondly, existing alternatives do not take sufficient account of the scale of ecological impact. Even if the inclusion of CO2 emissions is a sound decision, it represents only one dimension of ecological impact, leaving other crucial dimensions unexamined (see [Hickel, 2020](#) for the explanation on weaknesses). These are the limits that [Hickel \(2020\)](#) corrects in his HDI calculation. The author divides human development into a composite measure of ecological impact that integrates the two key indicators: per capita CO2 emissions and per capita material footprint. It is the first development index to adopt this dual approach. This measure of SDI is complete and better suited to the objective of our study insofar

⁴For simplicity, we refer to sustainable development index as sustainable development.

⁵Except the study of [Türe \(2013\)](#).

as we seek to assess the effectiveness of debt-for-nature swaps, which are implemented to meet a dual challenge (improving environmental sustainability and reducing public debt). Debt reduction can raise funds to finance the economy, which in turn will boost economic growth, create jobs and reduce poverty. We refer readers to the article by [Hickel \(2020\)](#) for more details on index construction, formulas and equations. Data updated to 2021 are available and can be accessed via this link [SDI](#).

Controls/matching variables. For the control variables, we select the control group of units with no debt-for-nature swaps that is on average as similar as possible to the treatment group of debt-for-nature swaps units in terms of relevant pre-treatment characteristics. Following the literature on the determinants of debt-for-nature swaps adoption and sustainable development, we select the following control variables: GDP per capita, debt service total, climatic vulnerability, property rights, and democracy polity. Given that better economic performance is likely to free up financial resources for the country and improve its financial conditions for coping with climate change, GDP per capita may be negatively correlated with the probability of adopting debt-for-nature swaps. Secondly, for a country to benefit from debt-for-nature, the government in power must have reached debt service thresholds and demonstrated progress in implementing fiscal reforms. As a result, total debt service is positively associated with the probability of adopting debt-for-nature ([Sommer et al., 2020](#)). Thirdly, and on the environmental criterion, a country can benefit from debt-for-nature provided it has at least one tropical forest with substantial biodiversity, or a forest that represents a large block of intact forest on a regional, continental or global scale ([UNCBD, 2001](#)). In addition, the urgency of the request must also be taken into account, focusing on the threats to biodiversity in the area to be protected in that country ([UNCBD, 2001](#)). As a result, high climatic vulnerability should be assigned to the probability of adopting a debt-for-nature swap. Finally, we turn to the importance of institutions in the debt-for-nature implementation. Indeed, repressive governments may not have well institutionalized property law systems, which can hamper the effective implementation of a debt-for-nature swap ([Rudel, 2005](#)). According to [Rudel \(2005\)](#), countries lacking institutionalized systems of property law can hamper the effectiveness of non-governmental organizations, which in turn negatively affects the effectiveness of debt-for-nature. According to [Lewis \(2000\)](#), debt-for-nature swaps are more likely to be implemented in democratic rather than in repressive nations. In the same vein, [UNCBD \(2001\)](#) argues that to benefit from debt-for-nature, a debtor nation must have a democratically elected government and demonstrate its commitment to guaranteeing human rights. However, it should be noted that some democratic or repressive governments in poor countries may not participate in unnatural debt swaps due to threats to national sovereignty ([Rudel, 2005](#)). Following [Rudel \(2005\)](#); [Lewis \(2000\)](#); and [UNCBD \(2001\)](#), we support the hypothesis that democracy and property rights are positively correlated with the probability of adopting a debt-for-nature. The definitions and sources of all variables, as well as the sample countries, are presented in tables [A4](#) in Appendix [B](#). For robustness

concerns, we add to these variables a several other potential determinants of DNS adoption (and sustainability development). We lagged these variables by one period because of econometrics problem (reverse causality) except democracy and property rights variables which are institutional variables.

To conclude this variable explanation exercise, we assess the performance of our entropy balancing method. To do so, we present some descriptive statistics obtained before and after weighting used to estimate the treatment effect of DNS adoption. We present the sample mean before weighting for country-year observations for the treatment group (DNS countries) and the control group (non-DNS countries) in table 1 columns ([1]-[2]). In column [3] of this table, we report the difference in means between the two groups. Indeed, DNS countries are characterized by high GDP per capita, high debt service total, high property rights, high democracy policy, and low climate vulnerability. These findings are consistent with the expected relationship between the probability of DNS adoption and the various control variables discussed above except GDP per capita and climate vulnerability. These differences across DNS and non-DNS countries demonstrate the importance of selecting an appropriate control group when computing the treatment effect of DNS to avoid incorrectly estimated treatment effects.

Table 2 shows in columns [1]-[2] the sample mean after weighting between the treatment group and the synthetic group obtained by entropy balancing, and column [3] shows the difference between the first two. Analysis of the two groups in this table reveals the effectiveness of entropy balancing, since the difference shown in the table is equal to 0. Consequently, entropy balancing allows us to construct a perfect control group, closely similar to the DNS countries based on observable characteristics, i.e. in terms of the mean values of the pre-treatment covariates.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics before weighting.

	[1]	[2]	[3]=[2]-[1]
	DNS	non-DNS	Difference
Lag GDP per capita (log)	8.901	8.307	-0.594
Lag debt service total	5.534	4.901	-0.633
Lag climate vulnerability	0.459	0.502	0.043
Property rights	39.84	36.18	-3.66
Democracy policy	5.824	2.22	-3.604
<i>Obs</i>	<i>461</i>	<i>1161</i>	

Table 2: Descriptive statistics after weighting.

	[1]	[2]	[3]=[2]-[1]
	DNS	non-DNS	Difference
Lag GDP per capita (log)	8.901	8.901	0
Lag debt service total	5.534	5.534	0
Lag climate vulnerability	0.459	0.459	0
Property rights	39.84	39.84	0
Democracy policy	5.824	5.824	0
<i>Obs</i>	<i>461</i>	<i>461</i>	
<i>Total of weights</i>	<i>461</i>	<i>1161</i>	

4.2 Descriptive statistics

A first look at the relationship between sustainable development and DNS can be revealed by exploring the unconditional correlation between these two variables. The results in line [2] of table A2 in Appendix A—which presents the unconditional correlation between these two variables—reveal that DNS is positively and significantly correlated with sustainable development at the 1% confidence level.

We now turn to the comparison of sustainable development between DNS et non-DNS countries. We explore this comparison in three ways. Firstly, we analyze graphically some key statistics offered by Fig.1. A closer look at this figure reveals a difference in the sustainable development between DNS and non-DNS countries. Indeed, DNS countries exhibit a median (the middle line of the box), 25th (bottom hinge of the box), and 75th (top hinge of the box) percentiles of sustainable development higher than non-DNS countries. This finding is justified by the fact that the median line, bottom hinge, and top hinge of the box for DNS countries are respectively higher those of non-DNS countries. While this figure exhibits a difference between DNS and non-DNS countries, it cannot assess its magnitude or significance. In other words, the simple comparison between the two groups may be biased. Based on the statistics reported in table 3, we are able to judge the significance of the difference between these two groups of countries through the statistics of the tests of difference of means. In Panel A, we compare average sustainable development between the two groups of countries, revealing that DNS adoption is associated with higher sustainable development. In fact, compared to the control group, countries benefiting of DNS have higher sustainable development, with a significant difference of 0.12 percentage points (t-stat=458 and p-value=0.000).

Finally, we analyze the change in average sustainable development within countries by calculating the average sustainable development before and after the adoption of DNS in Panel B. To avoid biasing the comparison between countries and to have a homogeneous sample, we have excluded countries that have not benefited from DNS. Unsurprisingly, the results show that sustainable development increases after DNS adoption. Compared with the results of the comparison between countries that have benefited from DNS and those that have not, the difference is 0.07 percentage points ($t\text{-stat}=207$ and $p\text{-value}=0.000$). These relationships, while not causal, give an idea of the treatment effect of DNS adoption and how to identify it. However, it would be misleading to estimate the effect of DNS on sustainable development simply by comparing sustainable development before and after DNS adoption. To avoid overestimating the effect of the policy, we use, as we saw above, countries without DNS as a synthetic control group to estimate the counterfactuals result.

Figure 1: Sustainable development by debt-for-nature swaps adoption

Note: In box plots, the lower and upper hinges of each box show the 25th and 75th percentiles of the samples, the line in the box indicates the respective medians, and the end-points of whiskers mark next adjacent values.

Table 3: Sustainable development by DNS adoption: mean-comparison tests

	<i>DNS</i>	<i>non-DNS</i>	<i>Diff</i>	<i>t-Test</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Panel A: Sustainable development	0.69	0.57	-0.12	457.9	0.000
	<i>Before</i>	<i>After</i>	<i>Diff</i>	<i>t-Test</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Sustainable development	0.61	0.68	0.07	206.7	0.000

5 Results

Using the synthetic controls in table 2, we estimate the effect of DNS adoption on sustainable development (ATT) in developing countries using the weighted least squares method. The results are reported in table 4. Columns [1]-[4] show the results of the second stage without the addition of the covariates used in the first stage of synthetic group construction. Column [1] excludes country and time fixed effects. Columns [2]-[3] include country— and time-specific effects respectively, while column [4] includes these two effects jointly. Finally, columns [5]-[8] repeat the exercise of columns [1]-[4] except by adding in each second-stage regression the covariates used in the first stage, namely GDP per capita, total debt service, climate vulnerability, property, and democracy policy. By including matching covariates in the second stage of entropy balancing, we have a strong chance of seeing matching quality increased (as in a randomized experiment), while controlling for country and year fixed effects eliminates any country— or year-specific effects as explained above. In each specification, the adoption of DNS significantly increases sustainable development at the 1% threshold in our sample of countries (columns [1]-[8]). Indeed, this result ranges from 0.07 percentage points (column [7]) to 0.15 percentage points (column [2])—a robust result given the relative stability of the coefficients in the 8 specifications of the table 4, with an average effect of 0.092 percentage points. In other words, DNS adoption increases on average sustainable development by 0.092 percentage points in DNS countries compared to non-DNS countries.

These results indicate that DNS can help achieve both human development and ecological sustainability— a goal now widely accepted and officially reflected in the Sustainable Development Goals. In fact, by increasing new investment, DNS boosts economic growth through job creation for the population. Moreover, by reducing the debt burden, DNS enable governments to use financial resources for other, more productive public policies. In other words, by reducing the debt burden, DNS increase the government’s capacity to finance sustainable development objectives. On the institutional level, given that the adoption of DNS requires the improvement of certain institutional and political indications such as democracy, rule of law and property rights, this would contribute to human development. Environmentally, DNS help protect biodiversity by combating deforestation, and improve ecological efficiency by reducing CO2 emissions and material footprints.

Our results contradict much of the transnational research and support theoretical arguments concerning the effectiveness of DNS in improving sustainable development. We can note that it does not appear that these exchanges are limited by their small size as some authors argue in relation to the scale of the sustainable development problem, nor that they are rendered totally ineffective due to the potential inability to solve the livelihood problems of local populations and the capacity problems of exchange participants.

Table 4: Debt-for-nature swaps and sustainable development—Baseline results

VARIABLES	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]	[7]	[8]
DNS adoption	0.0930*** (0.0098)	0.1455*** (0.0155)	0.0976*** (0.0098)	0.0886*** (0.0130)	0.0714*** (0.0070)	0.0876*** (0.0150)	0.0701*** (0.0069)	0.0809*** (0.0143)
Constant	-0.4568*** (0.0077)	-0.6035*** (0.0026)	-0.5067*** (0.0248)	-0.7124*** (0.0132)	-0.4931*** (0.1349)	-0.5857*** (0.2148)	-0.5141*** (0.1319)	-0.5647*** (0.2146)
Covariates	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country/FE	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
Year/FE	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
Observations	1,500	1,500	1,500	1,500	1,500	1,500	1,500	1,500
R-squared	0.0673	0.8841	0.0807	0.9200	0.5928	0.9202	0.5952	0.9253

Robust standard errors are in parentheses ***p < 0.01, **p < 0.05, *p < 0.1

6 Robustness

6.1 Alternative specifications

We examine the robustness of the paper’s main result when various considerations are taken into account in the analysis. We do this in two ways. Firstly, we control the effect of certain variables. Secondly, we exclude certain observations from our sample. Let’s start with the control of additional variables. Based on the literature on DNS and sustainable development, we select these variables and group them into four categories: *i-economic variables*: FDI, remittance inflows, net ODA, public expenditure, inflation rate, trade openness, public debt, exchange rate, total ODA biodiversity, agricultural value added, industry value added, commodity prices, and natural resources rents; *ii-political and institutional conditions*: internal conflict, external conflict, control of corruption, government effectiveness, rule of law, political stability, investment profile, and government stability; *iii-climate variables*: average temperature, average rainfall, and natural disasters; *iv-infrastructure and structural conditions*: ICT, human capital, electricity access, electricity consumption.

Let turn now to explanation and motivation on using of each variable. Many researchers argue that FDI stimulates economic growth in developing countries, either directly or indirectly through interactions with human capital (see [Makiela and Ouattara, 2018](#); [Choong et al., 2010](#)). For instance, [Gohou and Soumaré \(2012\)](#) argue that FDI can promote human development by reducing poverty and improving well-being. We take this into account by controlling for the effect of FDI. We control remittances flows because they stimulate economic growth ([Kraemer and Hartmann, 1993](#)), improve quality of life by reducing poverty ([Adams Jr and Page, 2005](#); [Taylor et al., 2003](#)), improve health outcomes, promote well-being and help reduce inequalities ([Nguea et al., 2022](#)). Remittances increase households’ productive capacity ex ante, helping to smooth consumption and growth ([Apeti, 2023](#)), and ex post protect households against unforeseen shocks ([Combes](#)

and Ebeke, 2011). However, remittances can adversely affect CO2 emissions and compromise sustainable development. Ahmad et al. (2019) explain how remittances can have a positive impact on CO2 emissions. For these authors, remittances do not directly influence CO2 emissions but indirectly through higher GDP per capita, higher consumption and savings, higher aggregate demand and bank deposits, financial development and industrial production, all of which contribute positively to economic growth.

Foreign Aid inflows can also influence sustainable development through the protection of environmental quality. In fact, the greater the flow of foreign aid, the lower the level of environmental degradation (Mahalik et al., 2021). Indeed, an emerging economy that receives more foreign financial aid will be able to increase its investments in running various programs to raise awareness of environmental quality protection for its population at different levels. However, foreign financing of energy will deteriorate environmental quality if it is invested more in the extraction of the mining and metal resources needed to strengthen economic growth (Mahalik et al., 2021). We take these declarations into account by adding ODA and ODA biodiversity as additional controls in our baseline regressions. In developing countries in particular, the basic needs of citizens are mainly met by public spending. At the same time, a large proportion of public financing comes from debt (see for instance, Gockel and Gray, 2011). For this reason, we introduced the public debt as an additional control variable to take into account the government's financial constraints because the debt ratio is expected to have a negative impact on welfare (Gockel and Gray, 2011), since the higher a country's debt, the more limited the government's ability to finance sustainable development (Boly et al., 2022).

We also control the effect of inflation to capture macroeconomic instability. Inflation is expected to have a negative impact on welfare, as high inflation increases commodity prices and has a direct impact on the poor (Gockel and Gray, 2011). In the same spirit, inflation can increase macroeconomic instability, which in turn will influence the volatility of household consumption and affect welfare. We control the effect of trade openness given its crucial role in raising average incomes and considerably stimulating economic growth (Dollar and Kraay, 2004), combined with its positive impact on sustainable development and its negative environmental effects (Kindo et al., 2024). The exchange rate can induce risk premiums for long-term agreements and increase production costs, thereby reducing growth in household consumption (see Apeti, 2023). In the same vein, exchange rate uncertainty can lead to high risk in investment decisions, threatening the performance of macroeconomic variables that are positively correlated with economic growth. Moreover, given that developing countries are heavily dependent on raw materials to ensure national production, exchange rate variations can affect the prices of domestic goods, thus shaping household consumption patterns (Oseni, 2016), affecting macroeconomic aggregates and reducing the sustainable development index. To take these provisions into account in our base regressions, we control for the exchange rate, commodity prices, and natural resources effects. Agricultural value added can affect the sustainable development in

developing countries. In fact, in most developing countries, the agricultural sector is recognized as a key factor in national development (WTO, 2014; FAO, 2009). At the same time, a large area of forest has been destroyed thanks to the intensification of agricultural activity (see Angelsen, 1999; Delacote, 2007; Galinato and Galinato, 2016; Liu et al., 2017). The industrialization effect is controlled by industry value added variable because the industrialization can explain the strong correlation between investment in equipment and economic growth in developing countries (Temple and Voth, 1998). This can improve the well-being of the population and affect sustainable development variables.

Secondly, we assume that political and institutional conditions can influence the relationship between DNS adoption and sustainable development. For example, a good application of the rule of law and a good level of corruption control can influence the relationship between DNS and sustainable development. This idea goes in the same direction with Rudel (2005), who shows that countries lacking institutionalized property law systems can firstly hamper the effectiveness of non-governmental organizations in the fight against deforestation, and secondly prevent the DNS from achieving their objectives. We control for these effects with variables related to control of corruption, the internal and external conflict, the government effectiveness, rule of law, the political stability, investment profile, and the government stability. These variables can affect sustainable development in different ways. According to Shahzad (2020), law enforcement increases financial capacity through strong tax collection, which can be used to advance the sustainable development program. The rule of law can promote efficient legal processes and good governance, and ensure the protection of natural resource property rights (Bhattarai and Hammig, 2001). Conflicts can worsen sustainable development indicators through the use of chemical weapons and the forced displacement of people from one area to another, reducing their well-being. Assessing the effect of conflict in Colombia, Ibáñez and Vélez (2008) find that internal conflict has caused forced displacement of people, resulting in welfare losses of 37% of the net present value of overall rural consumption over the lifetime. Third, we assume that our results may be influenced by climate conditions. As shown by Diwakar and Lacroix (2021), climate shocks prolong poverty through direct biophysical impacts, but also indirectly through various negative consequences and distress coping mechanisms in which vulnerable households engage. For Riley (2018) and Jack and Suri (2014), climate shocks have a negative impact on household consumption. According to Donadelli et al. (2017), temperature risk is associated with welfare costs amounting to 18.4% of the economic agent's lifetime utility, increasing exponentially with the magnitude of temperature's impact on total factor productivity. To control this effect, we include three climate variables, namely average temperature, average rainfall, and natural disasters.

Finally, we control the influence of infrastructure and structural factors. Today, ICTs offer significant opportunities to improve household living conditions in a wide range of areas, including social life, education, health and economic activities. For example,

its use can improve farmers' well-being by providing them with the information they need on inputs and technologies to improve farming activities, and by putting farmers in touch with profitable markets. According to [Mdoda and Mdiya \(2022\)](#), households with access to ICTs will succeed in increasing their agricultural production, by accessing market-oriented information, agricultural practices, climate information, information on new technologies and financial information. As a result, increased agricultural production combined with marketing information will help farmers increase their yields and improve household welfare. This in turn would increase sustainable development. For instance, in Kenya the use of ICT as an agricultural extension tool by smallholder farmers has the potential to improve yields and farmers' income, which will result in improved welfare ([Marwa et al., 2020](#)). This prompted [Nonvide \(2023\)](#) to assert that ICTs have the potential to effectively combat poverty and improve people's well-being. We use the ICT variable to control the effect of infrastructure. The ICT variable is a composite index of 4 sub-indicators that take into account both access to and use of ICT infrastructure: cell phone subscription per 100 people, fixed-line telephone subscription per 100 people, fixed-line broadband telephone subscription per 100 people, and percentage of individuals using the internet. [Herrera and Vincent \(2008\)](#) argue that cell phones (or mobile cell phones) could reduce the unpredictability of income and help smooth consumption. Next, we control the role of human capital, captured by years of schooling and enrolment in tertiary education on sustainable development and the adoption of DNS. Indeed, countries with higher-performing systems, higher levels of education and a large, better-educated majority may have better sustainable development indicators than their peers without such systems. In fact, the best-educated people easily understand climate issues and very often adopt eco-responsible behavior. We control the impact of access to energy, in particular access to electricity and electricity consumption. Indeed, energy, and electricity in particular, is recognized as a driving force behind economic, social and human development ([World Bank, 2001](#); [ESCAP, 2000](#)). Basically, access to electricity helps guarantee environmental sustainability (Goal 7 of United Nations Millennium Development Goals). In fact, electricity can be used to power water pumps that provide drinking water, thus facilitating the achievement of Goal 7, which is to reduce the proportion of the population without access to safe drinking water. Using renewable energies to supply electricity to the poor can contribute to the sustainable use of natural resources, as well as reducing greenhouse gas emissions, thereby protecting the local and global environment.

Let's turn to the second and final part of this exercise, which is the modification of our sample. Firstly, we exclude the pre-2000 period because of the major economic and political changes that can affect sustainable development. Secondly, we exclude countries that have recently benefited from DNS because of the potential time lag between the reforms and their expected effects. During the period of our study, several shocks occurred which could affect the sustainable development: political, economic, financial, ecological, and climatic. To do this, we exclude from our sample the years marked by the

financial crisis in 2008, the oil crisis in 2014, and the COVID-19 crisis in 2019. Finally, we know that developing countries are heavily dependent on natural resource revenues. This dependence could put implicit pressure on countries to over-exploit natural resources to finance development policies. For example, [Coulibaly \(2023\)](#) explains that countries that have signed up to resource-backed loans have a higher deforestation rate than their peers who have not. However, [Coulibaly \(2024\)](#) argues that resource-backed loans could help countries overcome difficulties in accessing financial markets and be an effective instrument for financing sustainable development. In fact, the signing of these loans is based on the assumption of natural resource endowment (see [Coulibaly, 2023](#); [Coulibaly, 2024](#)). Using a panel study for five European Union countries, [Balsalobre-Lorente et al. \(2018\)](#) posit that natural resources all contribute to emissions of greenhouse gases. The study concluded that there was an offset to the degradation of the environment due to abundant natural resources, renewable energy, and energy innovation. Other studies have examined the effects of natural resource extraction activities on the environment. In their study, [Kinda and Thiombiano \(2021\)](#) examined the relationship between extractive industry rents and forest cover loss in developing countries. At the same time, revenues from natural resources can be used to finance development, even if their extraction contributes to resource depletion ([Coulibaly, 2024](#)). We take account of these considerations by excluding from our observations the strong dependence on natural resource revenues captured by a dummy variable taking the value 1 if revenue from oil, coal, natural gas and minerals production is greater than the sample standard deviation, and 0 otherwise. We also exclude countries with high natural resource depletion rates, captured by a dummy variable taking the value 1 if the resource depletion rate is greater than the sample standard deviation, and 0 otherwise.

We report the new ATTs in tables [B1](#) and [B2](#) in Appendix [B](#). In table [B1](#), we report the results of the supplementary checks by group (columns [1]-[3]). In column [4], we test all four groups simultaneously. In table [B2](#), we report the results of the variables in disaggregated form (columns [1]-[29]). This allows us to take into account the heterogeneous effect that each variable might have. Finally, in columns [30]-[36] we report the results of the exclusion of observations likely to nuance our baseline results. Our results remain unchanged when numerous additional control variables are taken into account and also the sample is modified.

6.2 Alternative specifications

Our results show that DNS have a positive and statistically significant impact on sustainable development. We have seen that these results are robust to alternative specifications. We now check the robustness of these results using five different estimation methods: three impact estimation methods (propensity score matching, Difference-in-Difference and endogenous switching regression) and two methods to deal with potential endogeneity bias (GMM system and instrumental variable). We start this exercise with the **propensity**

score matching method. Indeed, as explained above, estimating a causal effect of DNS on sustainable development is a difficult task, as DNS adoption is probably not random but linked to specific macroeconomic, climatic and institutional conditions (generally referred to as preconditions), and therefore subject to selection bias. Although the method used in this paper addresses this selection bias problem, we use the propensity score matching method to strengthen our confidence. Developed by [Rosenbaum and Rubin \(1983\)](#), propensity score matching allows addressing the issue of self-selection in DNS adoption by pairing DNS countries (the treated group) with non-DNS countries (the control group) that are comparable in terms of observable characteristics that influence both DNS adoption and sustainable development (including, in particular, past sustainable development). As such, PSM allows mimicking DNS adoption as a randomized experiment, such as—conditional to some hypotheses that we discuss below—any difference in current sustainable development between matched DNS and non-DNS countries is attributable to the policy, i.e. DNS adoption.

As indicated by [Rosenbaum and Rubin \(1983\)](#) and detailed by [Apeti et al. \(2023\)](#), the PSM method is carried out in two stages. In the first step, we calculate a propensity score (PS) using a logit or probit model with DNS as dependent variable. In this study, we use a probit regression. Second, we use the counterfactuals obtained from the first step for the matching (see for instance [Chapel, 2022](#); [Coulibaly, 2024](#)). To carry out matching, the literature indicates that matching algorithms must be chosen. We follow [Combes et al. \(2024\)](#) in choosing eight matching algorithms. Firstly, we use N nearest neighbors, which matches each DNS country-year observation (processed) with the N nearest non-DNS country-year observations (unprocessed) with the nearest PS calculated in the first step - we choose the nearest (**N=1**), two nearest neighbors (**N=2**) and three nearest neighbors (**N=3**). Secondly, we use the radius method of [Dehejia and Wahba \(2002\)](#), which associates processed observations with unprocessed observations located at a given distance. For this purpose, we consider a small (**r = 0.045**), a medium (**r = 0.09**), and a wide (**r = 0.18**) radius based on the literature (see [Coulibaly, 2024](#); [Traore et al., 2023](#)). Thirdly, we use the kernel method developed by [Heckman et al. \(1998\)](#), which associates each treated observation with the distribution of untreated observations in the common support, with weights inversely proportional to the difference between the PS of treated and untreated observations. Fourthly and finally, we use the local linear correspondence developed by [Heckman et al. \(1998\)](#), which is close to kernel correspondence, except for the use of a linear term in its weighting function.

The results are shown in Table [B3](#) in Appendix B. But before interpreting the results, we check three tests for the validity and quality of our matching. First, the common support hypothesis, which requires the availability of comparable counterfactuals for each country-year observation with DNS (i.e. treated unit). To ensure that the treated and control groups are comparable (i.e. to check for overlap and the region of common support between the two groups), we rely on the comparison of minima and maxima as suggested

by [Caliendo and Kopeinig \(2008\)](#). Secondly, after estimation, we assess the validity of the matching procedure using the pseudo- R^2 test to check comparability between treated and control groups after matching (see for example [Sawadogo, 2020](#); [Coulibaly, 2024](#); [Apeti et al., 2023](#); [Caliendo and Kopeinig, 2008](#)). Finally, an important assumption is the conditional independence hypothesis, according to which the difference in outcome (i.e., sustainable development) between the treated and untreated groups results solely from the adoption of the DNS. Following [Rosenbaum \(2002\)](#) and [Caliendo and Kopeinig \(2008\)](#), we test this hypothesis using Rosenbaum’s bound sensitivity tests, which give an idea of the extent to which unobservable characteristics can bias the results of the matching exercise, and the standardized bias to test the conditional independence hypothesis against observable characteristics. All these tests confirm the quality of our matching and the results remain unchanged and robust.

The second alternative method we use in this paper is **Difference-in-Difference**. We use this method for two main reasons. Firstly, the main basis for interpreting the coefficients in table 4 as causal rests on the assumption that treated and untreated countries would follow similar trends in the absence of DNS adoption ([Bertrand et al., 2004](#)). However, recent studies suggest that this is still not the case and that this approach often produces biased results (see [Roth et al., 2023](#)). In fact, the problem stems from the irregular timing of the DNS and their variable impact over time and from country to country. This problem is known in the literature as «staggered adoption», which relies on the presence of several groups and several treatment periods (see for instance, [Athey and Imbens, 2022](#); [Callaway and Sant’Anna, 2021](#)). Consequently, the coefficient obtained in table 4 may not accurately reflect the real average effect of treatment on countries that have benefited from DNS (ATT). Secondly, forbidden comparisons can introduce bias into estimates in the context of a two-factor fixed-effects (TWFE) model ([Bertrand et al., 2004](#); [Callaway and Sant’Anna, 2021](#)). In other words, when the estimates use the first units as a control for units treated later, the entropy balancing method lacks validity for identifying the impact of DNS on sustainable development. With thirty-two cohorts of observations—country processed at different times throughout the year, the likelihood of heterogeneous effects is significant, increasing the risk of bias. Consequently, we adopted recently developed estimators robust to the biases inherent in conventional TWFE models. We follow [Callaway and Sant’Anna \(2021\)](#), who identify specific ATTs for each cohort g and year t and aggregate them to present «event study» type figures. This procedure allows for heterogeneity of treatment effects, thus avoiding incorrect comparisons. [Callaway and Sant’Anna \(2021\)](#) method is suitable for our model, as it calculates ATTs by group before and after DNS adoption. We estimate the model using inverse probability weighting, in which treated countries are compared to never-treated countries with the same probability of receiving debt relief in the form of debt-for-nature swaps. Next, we use doubly robust methods, two based on inverse probability weighting ([Abadie, 2005](#)) and based on combination of inverse probability with stabilized inverse probability

weighting and ordinary least squares. The estimation of these probabilities is based on macroeconomic, political, environmental, geographical and socio-economic characteristics, captured by our covariates as defined in tables [1] - [2]. The new ATTs reported in table B4, Panel B show that DNS positively and significantly affect sustainable development.

Thirdly, we use **endogenous switching regression models** for two main reasons: *i*- endogenous switching regression models jointly estimate selection and outcome equations through a full information maximum likelihood (FIML) estimator (see [Asfaw et al., 2012](#); [Carter and Milon, 2005](#); [Nonvide, 2019](#)); *ii*- endogenous switching regression models enable counterfactual analysis. In other words, the model will make it possible to assess how much the level of sustainable development of a DNS non-beneficiary would have improved if he or she had benefited from DNS, and the loss for the DNS beneficiary in the event of rigorous non-monitoring. Indeed, the estimation of the endogenous switching regression (ESR) model consists of separate estimates for countries that have benefited from DNS and countries that have not. This suggests that the adoption of DNS becomes the selection criterion indicating to which regime a country belongs. Next, the level of sustainable development is observed for both groups (see [Nonvide, 2019](#); [Di Falco et al., 2011](#)). To compare the expected results (level of sustainable development) of DNS countries (a) with those of non-DNS countries (b), and to study the expected results in counterfactual cases (c) that countries have not adopted, and (d) that non-DNS countries have adopted, we follow recent studies such as [Asfaw et al. \(2012\)](#); [Di Falco et al. \(2011\)](#); [Nonvide \(2019\)](#); [Heckman et al. \(1998\)](#); [Carter and Milon \(2005\)](#). Table B5 shows the expected levels of sustainable development under actual and counterfactual conditions. Cells (a) and (b) represent the expected sustainable development observed in the sample for DNS and non-DNS countries respectively. We observed that the expected sustainable development of DNS countries was higher than that of non-DNS countries. However, on the basis of this simple comparison, it could be misleading to attribute the difference in sustainable development to the adoption of DNS by countries. In counterfactual case (c), it has been clearly demonstrated that the treatment effect for DNS countries is 0.1073. This equates to a difference of 11.33% in average sustainable development.⁶ In other words, if DNS countries had not benefited from DNS, their sustainable development would have been reduced by 11.33%. In counterfactual case (d), if non-DNS countries had benefited from DNS, their sustainable development would have been increased by 1.78%. From this point of view, the transitional heterogeneity effect is positive, implying that the effect of DNS on sustainable development is significantly higher for those countries that actually used DNS for their intended purposes than for those that did not. These results confirm our baseline hypothesis that DNS have a significant impact on sustainable development.⁷

⁶Note that the treatment effect in this unit is interpreted as a percentage difference. In fact, when the outcome variable is log-transformed, multiplying TT by 100 is an approximation. In other words, the exact percentage difference is given by $[100*(e^{TT} - 1)]$, where e is the exponential e and TT the average treatment effect provided by the analysis of the log-transformed variable (see [Asfaw et al., 2012](#)).

⁷The results of the treatment effects confirming our baseline results are shown in Fig.2 in Appendix.

Fourthly, as we saw earlier, there are potential shortcomings due to data limitations, in particular the use of a dummy variable defined by the year of DNS adoption, which does not take into account the level of evolution of the amounts of funds allocated to countries under DNS transactions. We use AfDB (2022) information on DNS transactions to build a database. There are two types of transaction in AfDB (2022) that we have identified, namely transactions on the face value of cancelled debt and funds that were earmarked for the environment. We collect these data and carry out a **cross-sectional analysis**. Using these data in **cross-sectional regression**, our results show that debt relief in the form of DNS positively affects sustainable development, with environmental funds being more significant (see table B6, columns [3]-[4]). This is in line with our baseline results, but also draws the attention of policy-makers in debtor countries and donors to the fact that debt cancellation alone is not enough, and that funds need to be deployed in the projects concerned in order to grasp the real impact of DNS.

Finally, we use **two-stage GMM systems** and the **instrumental variable method** to address potential endogeneity biases that might arise in DNS processing and adoption. Although the endogenous switching regression models method addresses this concern, we are keen to reinforce the confidence and quality of our results. First, the two-stage GMM method combines the level and first-difference equations into a system, and estimates them using lagged differences and levels of explanatory variables as instruments. As a result, and given that, compared with the GMM difference estimator, the GMM system takes more instruments into account by adding a second equation to improve estimation efficiency, we address the problem of instrument proliferation by reducing the instrument matrix (Blundell and Bond, 1998; Roodman, 2009). In addition, we use Windmeijer (2005)'s finite-sample correction to reduce the possibility of erroneous precision, so that standard errors are not biased downwards. In addition to the two-stage GMM method, which uses only internal instruments, we address the endogeneity problem with the Instrumental Variables (IV) method, which uses external instruments (see Sommer et al., 2020). This method allows us not only to overcome the problem of instrument proliferation in GMM, but also the main criticism of GMM, which is the «black box» for certain researchers (see Soto, 2009). The results reported in table B6, columns [1]-[2] confirm our baseline finding: DNS adoption considerably increases sustainable development in developing countries after endogeneity treatment.

In sum, the robustness section confirms—by and large—our baseline finding: DNS adoption significantly increases sustainable development when considering alternative specifications, samples, measures of the main variables, or estimation methods.

6.3 Is the debt-for-nature achieve its both main objectives?

The main objectives of debt-for-nature swaps are to improve environmental sustainability and public indebtedness, thereby contributing to the stability of the international financial system. However, the effect of DNS on each of these variables is controversial in

the literature. No consensus has yet been reached on the ability of DNS to achieve its objectives. In practice, debt cancellation undoubtedly frees up fiscal space for the country to finance the fight against climate change, poverty, inequality and so on. At the same time, additional fiscal space can lead to discretionary spending by the government (see [Neuenkirch and Neumeier, 2016](#)), so that the country returns to its original fiscal position. In any case, the first objective feeds the second, i.e., when the first is achieved, it boosts the government’s ability to pursue the second objective. Although the focus of our paper is very much on the second objective that debt-for-nature swaps seek to achieve, in this section we deepen the debate by examining the effect of DNS on public debt and deforestation. This will enable us to make fairly comprehensive policy recommendations for all stakeholders involved in DNS transactions (NGOs, government creditors and debtors, national and international institutions, etc.). The results reported in Panel A, columns [1]-[2] of table B4 show that DNS significantly reduce the stock of external debt. These results confirm that DNS can be an effective instrument for reducing debt, contradicting the studies of [Cassimon et al. \(2011\)](#) and are in line with [Heller \(2005\)](#). While in columns [3]-[4], our results indicate that DNS significantly increase forest land biocapacity per capita in developing countries.

7 Heterogeneity test

Having established the robustness of our baseline results under various alternative specifications, the current section explores its sensitivity according to DNS type, over time and in relation to several structural characteristics.

7.1 Disaggregated effects of debt-for-nature swaps

We disaggregate DNS into two types of transaction: bilateral and multi-party DNS. The idea behind this exercise is that these two types of transactions could have a heterogeneous effect on sustainable development, given their size, survival, requirements, etc. We report the results in table B7, columns [1]-[2]. The results suggest that both types of DNS have a significant impact on sustainable development, with a higher amplitude for bilateral DNS.⁸ A possible explanation for this heterogeneous effect lies in the size, type and requirements of the donors, and the stakeholders involved in the DNS agreements. In terms of size, this effect can be explained by the fact that bilateral DNS are large and multi-party DNS in terms of transaction volume. In fact, DNS are subject to a great deal of criticism due to the insignificant amounts of debt cancelled. As a result, the larger the size, the greater the impact. The second channel is the donor’s requirement, which can be observed in two areas: pre-agreement and post-agreement. In the pre-agreement phase, the DNS bilateral agreement requires the country to present a sound economic situation, and to possess

⁸It should be noted that most bilateral DNS are granted by the United States.

governance based on the rule of law and democracy. The post-agreement phase is linked to an examination of the DNS granted in the past, and whether the funds were actually directed towards improving environmental quality. Another possible explanation for this result is that multi-party DNS involves many partners in the transactions (NGOs, private and public institutions, etc.), which slows down the signing of agreements, making it even more tedious for countries that need a fairly simple and fast system for obtaining funds and investing. We refer readers to the studies of [Sommer et al. \(2020\)](#) and [AfDB \(2022\)](#) for a better understanding of the mechanisms of the two types of DNS.

7.2 The effect of debt-for-nature swaps over time

In this section, we examine the evolution of the effect of DNS adoption on sustainable development over time, using a time-varying treatment effect. This dynamic effect can be used to isolate a potential time lag between the date of DNS adoption and its (significant) effect on sustainable development. The ATTs estimated for the year of DNS adoption ($t=0$) and for the four years following the year of adoption ($t=1, 2, 3, 4$) in table B8 reveal the existence of a dynamic effect of DNS adoption. This effect appears as soon as DNS is adopted, and increases over time to approach the (average) magnitude of our reference effect five years after policy adoption. This dynamic effect, which appears as soon as the policy is adopted, can be explained by the improvement in macroeconomic, institutional and political conditions imposed by certain donors such as the United States (see [Sommer et al., 2020](#)), which will eventually improve the sustainable development indicators. Donor and debtor countries should therefore work harder on these conditions and requirements to maintain the persistence effect of DNS over time.

7.3 The role of structural and institutional factors

Our results show that the adoption of DNS increases sustainable development in developing countries. In this section, we explore the sensitivity of the effect of DNS adoption on sustainable development in relation to various structural characteristics, namely fiscal conditions, business cycle phase, institutional quality, commitment to environmental conventions, and political program.

Firstly, we distinguish the countries in our sample according to their level of development, using IMF classifications as in [Apeti and Edoh \(2023\)](#). Even if geographically close countries have a certain degree of simultaneity in terms of the structure of their economies, as **Waldo Tobler's** law shows (see [Klemm and Van Parys, 2012](#)), developing countries present significant heterogeneity. To account for this heterogeneity, we divide the countries in our sample into two groups: low-income countries and emerging countries. The results presented in table B9 columns [1]-[2], show that DNS adoption increases sustainable development in both groups. However, the effect of DNS is higher in low-income countries than in emerging countries.

Secondly, we analyze the degree of vulnerability of each country. To do this, we divided our sample into two groups, according to the standard deviation of the sample: countries with high climate vulnerability and those with low climate vulnerability. In other words, we construct a dummy variable which takes the value 1 if climate vulnerability score exceeds standard deviation and 0 otherwise. The results in columns [3]-[4] of table B9 show two possible effects. Debt-for-nature swaps are more effective in countries more vulnerable to climate shocks than their peers non vulnerable. These results should draw the attention of donor countries to the criteria for selecting beneficiary countries. In fact, they should be more interested in low-income countries that are more vulnerable to climate change.

Thirdly, we start from the idea that good institutions can promote the effectiveness of political reforms, and we analyze the sensitivity of our results to the role of institutions, and in particular to the control of corruption. We distinguish between countries with low and high levels of corruption control, based on the median of the sample. The results in table B9, columns [5]-[6] show that DNS increase sustainable development whatever the level of institutional quality. However, we note that the effect of DNS on sustainable development is greater in the context of better institutional quality, i.e. higher levels of corruption control.

Fourthly, we analyze the role of democracy, since a necessary but not sufficient condition to benefit from DNS is to have a good application of democracy (see Sommer et al., 2020). We distinguish between low- and high-democracy countries according to the sample median. The results in table B9, columns [7]-[8] show that DSN increases sustainable development whatever the level of democracy. However, we note that the effect of DSN on sustainable development is greater in the context of better democracy application. These results reveal that the effectiveness of DNS does not necessarily depend on the political regime, but its magnitude can improve in the case of a democratic regime.

Fifth, we follow Sargent et al. (1981) and Leeper (1991), in examining the influence of fiscal policy in order to test the fiscal dominance hypothesis. In fact, the DNS could free up fiscal space for the country and lead to discretionary spending, thus inducing a flexible fiscal policy. The estimates in columns [9]-[10] of table B9 indicate that a good fiscal stance favors (as measured by median government expenditure in percent of GDP) the effect of DNS on sustainable development, while poor fiscal conditions inhibit the effectiveness of DNS. The results in columns [11]-[12] show that DNS are also more effective in the presence of a strong fiscal policy (captured by the median of public debt) than in a situation of loose fiscal policy.

Sixth, we analyze the effectiveness of DNS in forest-endowed countries. To do this, we divided our sample into two groups, according to the median of the sample: countries with a strong forest planting policy and those with a weak forest planting policy based on standard deviation of planted forest (% of forest area). The results in columns [13]-[14] of table B9 show that the effect of DNS on sustainable development seems to be higher in

countries that plant a lot of trees and protect the forest even though in two sub-samples we found that DNS improved forest protection. These results are perfectly in line with those found in the literature (see for instance [Sommer et al., 2020](#); [Shandra et al., 2011](#)).

Seventh, we analyze the effectiveness of DNS in the presence of Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative (EITI) membership. Some studies have shown, for example, that EITI membership improves the quality of institutions ([Villar and Papyrakis, 2017](#); [Villar, 2022](#)), combats deforestation ([Kindo et al., 2024](#)), increases tax revenues ([Kinda and Thiombiano, 2021](#)), improves the investment climate and economic development ([Sovacool, 2020](#)), and promotes governance reform ([Aronnd et al., 2019](#)). Under these conditions, we test the hypothesis that EITI can amplify the effect of DNS on sustainable development in developing countries. We follow [Kindo et al. \(2024\)](#) in constructing the variable EITI taking the value 1 if the country has joined EITI and 0 otherwise. The results in columns [15]-[16] of table [B9](#) show that the effect of DNS on sustainable development seems to be higher in countries that have joined EITI.

Eighth, we analyze the effectiveness of DNS as a function of the country's engagement in international environmental conventions. To do this, we divided our sample into two groups, based on the sample mean: high-engagement countries and low-engagement countries. The results in columns [17]-[18] of Table [B9](#) show that the effect of DNS on sustainable development seems to be higher in countries with a high level of engagement to environmental conventions.

Finally, columns [19]-[20] reveal that DNS increase sustainable development in both good and bad periods of the business cycle, but to a greater extent in the bad phase. One possible explanation could be that, in the high phase of the business cycle, the country may have less recourse to debt relief in the form of DNS. This could have an effect on the amount of DNS transactions during this period, and in turn reduce their scale.

8 Transmission channels

Our results show that DNS increase sustainable development. In this section, we provide evidence on (some of) the potential channels through which DNS affect sustainable development. In this article, we identify five main channels⁹: *(a)* a reduction in the rate of natural resource depletion; *(b)* a reduction in CO2 emissions; *(c)* an increase in the stock of public capital captured by public investment; *(d)* an increase in economic output represented by GDP growth; *(e)* an improvement in well-being measured by the human development index (excluding the ecological dimension). Given that there is no single technique in the literature for testing transmission channels, we have kept our basic

⁹It should be noted that these channels are not exhaustive and other channels such as: volatility of fiscal policy measured by the standard deviation of government expenditure 5-years of window; public debt; institutional quality measured by a composite index of corruption, government stability, political stability, democracy, rule of law; deforestation; greenhouse gas emissions; resource rents have been tested as part of this study but the statistics are not reported in the paper which could be available on request.

model for this exercise. In column [1] of table 5, we show a negative and statistically significant relationship between DNS and resource depletion. In fact, DNS force governments to invest in green projects, biodiversity protection, and renewable and non-renewable resources, thereby curbing resource depletion. Another explanation is that to benefit from DNS, the country must have a resource that can be protected or preserved. This can act as a disincentive to the abusive exploitation of natural resources. In column [2] of table 5, we show a negative and statistically significant relationship between DNS and CO2 emissions. As we saw above, DNS increase forest land biocapacity, which will necessarily affect CO2 emissions, as forests are known for their carbon sequestration. Reducing resource depletion and CO2 emissions improves the sustainable development index, since they are included in the SDI calculation (see [Hickel, 2020](#)). In columns [3];[4]; and [5], we show that DNS have a positive and statistically significant impact on public investment, economic growth and well-being respectively. Indeed, DNS are granted with the aim of investing in environmental preservation. These investments will create jobs for the population, reduce intensive agricultural activity which destroys the forest, create additional revenue for the government, which will boost economic growth, which in turn will serve to reduce poverty and inequality, and improve the well-being of the population.

In addition to these channels, we found that public debt reduction is a potential one. As explained above, before us, evidence was found in the literature showing the negative effect of DNS on public debt. For instance, [Jones and Campos \(2023\)](#) estimate that since 2015, DNS have restructured around 3 billion USD representing up to 1.6% of national GDP. Thus, by reducing public debt, DNS provide governments with additional financial resources, which will enable them to finance poverty, income inequality and climate change, thereby significantly increasing long-term sustainable development.

Table 5: Debt-for-nature swaps and sustainable development: transmission channels

VARIABLES	[1] Resource depletion	[2] CO2 emissions	[3] Total public investment	[4] GDP growth	[5] Well-being
DNS dummy	-0.7121*** (0.1384)	-0.1516*** (0.0425)	0.1771*** (0.0438)	0.0120*** (0.0046)	0.0089*** (0.0025)
Constant	8.1871*** (2.4316)	-6.9568*** (1.4863)	1.5616 (0.9660)	1.1256*** (0.1358)	0.2700*** (0.0410)
Covariates	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country/FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year/FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	1,582	1,622	1,528	1,622	1,582
R-squared	0.8380	0.9752	0.6453	0.9979	0.9910

Robust standard errors based in brackets. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

9 Conclusion

This paper analyzes whether the adoption of debt-for-nature swaps improves sustainable development in developing countries. Using entropy balancing to control for endogeneity on a large sample of 127 developing countries over the period 1990-2020, our study concludes that debt-for-nature swaps increase sustainable development in countries that have benefited from them, compared with countries that have not benefited from this public debt relief program. This result is robust to several alternative specifications, including extending the vector of control variables, modifying the sample, using an alternative treatment definition, and using competing estimation methods. Further estimates show that if the treated countries had not benefited from DNS, their sustainable development indices would have decreased by 11%, whereas if the untreated countries had benefited from DNS, their indices would have increased by around 2%. In addition, our findings suggest that we should not be pessimistic about expanding the DNS, as they are effective in improving sustainable development and also helping reduce external debt. However, heterogeneity tests show that the effect of debt-for-nature swaps may depend on the type of debt-for-nature swap transaction, the time perspective and certain structural factors. In fact, such characteristics can promote or, in contrast, inhibit the effectiveness of the environmental and budgetary framework and suggest that certain conditions need to be met to expect DNS to have a favorable effect in terms of increasing sustainable development. Finally, we provide evidence that reduced resource depletion and CO2 emissions, increased investment, improved economic growth and well-being (measured by life expectancy at birth, expected years of schooling and average years of schooling, and gross national income per capita) are potential transmission channels through which debt-for-nature swaps affect sustainable development.

This study makes a significant contribution to the literature by proposing a rigorous empirical assessment of the effectiveness of debt-for-nature swaps in sustainable development in developing countries. Unlike previous work, which is often descriptive or focused on case studies, it uses an innovative quantitative approach based on the entropy balancing method to correct for selection biases linked to the non-random adoption of DNS. It is also distinguished by the use of Hickel's Sustainable Development Index, which integrates both human and ecological dimensions, offering a more comprehensive measure of sustainability. By incorporating country- and time- fixed effects, the study addresses the methodological limitations identified in previous research and reinforces the robustness of the results. Finally, by distinguishing between bilateral and multi-party DNS, it enables a more detailed analysis of the effects according to the type of operation, thus enriching the debate on debt management policies in the service of the climate.

This article calls on creditor governments to reauthorize and extend the program by allocating more funds to the program or by relaxing eligibility criteria to increase the number of countries eligible for the program. In addition, another promising approach could

be to integrate climate concerns into existing debt relief programs such as HIPC/IADM, by raising awareness among policymakers and helping developing countries to take full account of climate change mitigation and adaptation issues when formulating their national development strategies. We were constrained by the availability of data on DNS amounts, forcing us to use a DNS dummy variable. This is a limitation of this study; future research should reexamine the relationship examined here using data on DNS amounts when they become available.

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Appendix A Data and sample

Table A1 – Descriptive statistics of the main variables

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
SDI	3100	0.6	0.141	0.207	0.837
Lag.GDP per capita (log)	3429	8.676	1.02	6.079	11.373
Lag.debt service total	2926	4.746	5.978	0.001	102.222
Lag.climatic vulnerability	2725	0.481	0.085	0.304	0.707
Property rights	2742	39.893	18.463	0	90
Democracy polity	3116	2.251	6.076	-10	10

Table A2 – Correlation matrix of the main variables

Variables	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]	[7]
[1] SDI	1.000						
[2] Debt-for-nature swaps	0.346 (0.000)	1.000					
[3] Lag.GDP per capita (log)	0.570 (0.000)	0.138 (0.000)	1.000				
[4] Lag.debt service total	0.194 (0.000)	0.056 (0.003)	0.320 (0.000)	1.000			
[5] Lag.climatic vulnerability	-0.544 (0.000)	-0.198 (0.000)	-0.818 (0.000)	-0.390 (0.000)	1.000		
[6] Property rights	0.030 (0.148)	0.052 (0.006)	0.441 (0.000)	0.190 (0.000)	-0.414 (0.000)	1.000	
[7] Democracy polity	0.229 (0.000)	0.205 (0.000)	0.337 (0.000)	0.103 (0.000)	-0.243 (0.000)	0.461 (0.000)	1.000

Note: the p-values are in brackets.

Table A3 – List of debt-for-nature (DNS) and Non-DNS countries

Treated countries (DNS)	Untreated countries (non-DNS)		
Argentina	Afghanistan	Georgia	Portugal
Bangladesh	Albania	Greece	Puerto Rico
Belize	Angola	Grenada	Romania
Bosnia & Herzegovina	Antigua and Barbuda	Guinea	Rwanda
Brazil	Armenia	Guyana	Samoa
Bulgaria	Azerbaijan	Haiti	Sao Tome and Principe
Cameroon	Bahamas	India	Senegal
Chile	Barbados	Iran	Serbia
Colombia	Belarus	Iraq	Sierra Leone
Ecuador	Benin	Ireland	Slovenia
Egypt	Bhutan	Kazakhstan	Solomon Islands
El Salvador	Botswana	Kenya	Somalia
Ghana	Burkina Faso	Kyrgyz Republic	South Africa
Guatemala	Burundi	Lebanon	South Sudan
Guinea-Bissau	Cambodia	Lesotho	Sri Lanka
Honduras	Central African Republic	Liberia	St. Lucia
Indonesia	Chad	Libya	Sudan
Jamaica	Comoros	Malawi	Suriname
Jordan	Congo, Dem Rep	Maldives	Tajikistan
Mexico	Congo, Rep	Mali	Thailand
Mozambique	Cote d'Ivoire	Mauritania	Togo
Nicaragua	Croatia	Mauritius	Tonga
Nigeria	Cuba	Moldova	Turkey
Panama	Cyprus	Mongolia	Turkmenistan
Paraguay	Djibouti	Montenegro	Uganda
Peru	Dominica	Morocco	Ukraine
Seychelles	Equatorial Guinea	Myanmar	Uzbekistan
Syria	Eritrea	Nauru	Vanuatu
Tanzania	Ethiopia	Nepal	Venezuela
Tunisia	Fiji	Niger	Yemen
Uruguay	Gabon	Pakistan	Zimbabwe
Vietnam	Gambia	Papua New Guinea	

Table A4 – List of variables and their sources

Variables	Definition	Sources
Sustainable development index		
Measures the ecological efficiency of human development Hickel (2020)		
1. Dependent variable		
2. Treatment variable		
3. Baseline model control variables or covariates		
GDP per capita	GDP per capita, PPP (constant 2017 international \$)	WDI
Debt service total	Total service debt (% of GNI)	WDI
Climate vulnerability scores	Measure climate change vulnerability	ND-Gain Université Notre Dame
Property rights	Index ranging from 0 to 100	Economic Freedom Scores Database
Democracy regimes	Index ranging from -10 to 10	Polity V
4. Additional control variables		
Resources rents	Continuous	WDI
Internal conflict	Continuous	ICRG
External conflict	Continuous	ICRG
Control of corruption	Index ranging from 0 to 100	WGI, Kaufmann et al. (2011)
Governance effectiveness	Continuous	ICRG
Rule of law	Continuous	Tenell et al. (2016)
Political stability	Index ranging from -2 to 2	WGI, Kaufmann et al. (2011)
Investment profile	Continuous	ICRG
Disasters index	Index ranging from 0 to 100	FERDI database, Guillaumont (2009), Feindouno and Goujon (2016)
ICT	Continuous	ND-Gain Université Notre Dame
Years of schooling	Continuous	Hickel (2020)
Access to electricity	Continuous	WDI
Electric power consumption	Continuous	WDI
Fossil fuel production	Continuous	WDI
Resource depletion	Continuous	WDI
Total external debt stocks in % of GDP	Continuous	FAO
Forest land biocapacity per capita	Continuous	WDI
FDI	Continuous	WDI
Remittance inflows	Continuous	WDI
ODA	Continuous	WDI
Public expenditure	Continuous	IMF, WEO
Inflation rate	Continuous	WDI
Trade openness	Continuous	WDI
Public debt	Continuous	Ali Abbas et al. (2011)
Exchange rate	Continuous	Penn World Table 10.0
ODA biodiversity	Continuous	OECD – processed by Our World in Data
Agricultural value added	Continuous	WDI
Industry value added	Continuous	WDI
Commodity prices	Continuous	Gruss and Kebhaj (2019)

Appendix B Robustness checks

Table B1 – DNS and sustainable development: additional variables by group

	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]
Economic variables		Political and institutional conditions	Climate variables	Infrastructure and structural	All
VARIABLES	group	group	group	conditions group	group
DNS dummy	0.0431*** (0.0081)	0.0570*** (0.0190)	0.0800*** (0.0140)	0.0214*** (0.0067)	0.0191* (0.0107)
Constant	0.1154 (0.2594)	-0.3362 (0.2928)	-0.4046* (0.2268)	-1.1614*** (0.2146)	-1.9891*** (0.3360)
Covariates	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country/FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year/FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	885	759	1,383	933	382
R-squared	0.9666	0.9579	0.9403	0.9540	0.9895

Notes: Robust standard errors based in brackets. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

Table B2 – DNS and sustainable development: additional variables desegregated and excluding observations

VARIABLES	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]	[7]	[8]	[9]	[10]	[11]	[12]
<i>Additional variables</i>												
	FDI	Remittance inflows	ODA	Public expenditure	Inflation rate	Trade openness	Public debt	exchange rate	ODA biodiversity	Agricultural value added	Industry value added	Commodity prices
DNS dummy	0.0725*** (0.0135)	0.0809*** (0.0143)	0.0747*** (0.0131)	0.0859*** (0.0141)	0.0522*** (0.0098)	0.0813*** (0.0134)	0.0635*** (0.0154)	0.0822*** (0.0137)	0.0557*** (0.0131)	0.0890*** (0.0149)	0.0828*** (0.0139)	0.0853*** (0.0133)
Constant	-0.6275*** (0.2136)	-0.6480*** (0.2152)	-0.6712*** (0.2069)	-0.4893** (0.2509)	-0.7182*** (0.2127)	-0.2390 (0.2125)	-0.5391*** (0.2087)	-0.5395*** (0.2083)	-0.5173** (0.2351)	-0.2965 (0.2150)	-0.5201** (0.2241)	0.4419* (0.2294)
Covariates	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country/FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year/FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	1,499	1,441	1,467	1,268	1,393	1,422	1,342	1,458	1,097	1,474	1,470	1,403
R-squared	0.9268	0.9269	0.9272	0.9239	0.9294	0.9241	0.9367	0.9334	0.9405	0.9273	0.9459	0.9430
[13]	[14]	[15]	[16]	[17]	[18]	[19]	[20]	[21]	[22]	[23]	[24]	
Resources rents	Internal conflict	External conflict	Control of corruption	Governance effectiveness	Rule of law	Political stability	Investment profile	Government stability	Average temperature	Average rainfall	Disasters index	
DNS dummy	0.0804*** (0.0141)	0.0818*** (0.0141)	0.0749*** (0.0133)	0.0746*** (0.0114)	0.0610*** (0.0142)	0.0810*** (0.0142)	0.0814*** (0.0142)	0.0828*** (0.0142)	0.0797*** (0.0142)	0.0810*** (0.0142)	0.0828*** (0.0144)	
Constant	-0.5983*** (0.2187)	-0.3819 (0.2347)	-0.4358* (0.2348)	-0.5906** (0.2319)	-0.6536** (0.2375)	-0.5408** (0.2179)	-0.4212* (0.2379)	-0.4314* (0.2364)	-0.4939** (0.2187)	-0.5640** (0.2392)	-0.6947*** (0.2042)	
Covariates	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Country/FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Year/FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Observations	1,500	1,186	1,186	1,329	976	1,500	1,186	1,186	1,500	1,472	1,411	
R-squared	0.9254	0.9324	0.9314	0.9297	0.9458	0.9253	0.9314	0.9313	0.9255	0.9268	0.9375	
[25]	[26]	[27]	[28]	[29]	[30]	[31]	[32]	[33]	[34]	[35]	[36]	
VARIABLES	ICT	Tertiary education	Years of schooling	Access to electricity	Electric power consumption	New DNS adopters	Financial crisis	Petroleum crisis	COVID-19 crisis	Dependence on income resources	Resource depletion	
DNS dummy	0.0376*** (0.0093)	0.0699*** (0.0128)	0.0701*** (0.0127)	0.0652*** (0.0117)	0.0527*** (0.0114)	0.0791*** (0.0157)	0.0834*** (0.0145)	0.0809*** (0.0146)	0.0809*** (0.0143)	0.0280*** (0.0092)	0.0732*** (0.0126)	
Constant	-1.0298*** (0.2046)	-0.3909* (0.2153)	-0.9795*** (0.2195)	-0.9943*** (0.2109)	-0.8032*** (0.1915)	-0.5888** (0.2411)	-0.5550** (0.2195)	-0.5976*** (0.2214)	-0.5647*** (0.2146)	-1.1348*** (0.2719)	-0.6944*** (0.2427)	
Covariates	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Country/FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Year/FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Observations	1,500	1,463	1,500	1,427	1,012	1,285	1,485	1,428	1,500	627	1,186	
R-squared	0.9395	0.9304	0.9320	0.9305	0.9422	0.9253	0.9222	0.9248	0.9253	0.9821	0.9292	

Robust standard errors based on 50 replications in brackets. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

Table B3 – DNS and sustainable development: using propensity score matching

Dependent Variable :	1-Nearest Neighbor		2-Nearest Neighbor		3-Nearest Neighbor		Radius Matching		Local linear regression		Kernel
	Matching	r=0.005	Matching	r=0.005	Matching	r=0.005	Matching	r=0.01	Matching	r=0.01	Matching
Sustainable development											
ATT	0.0627*** (0.0148)	0.0654*** (0.0146)	0.0629*** (0.0114)	0.0640*** (0.0078)	0.0698*** (0.0064)	0.0868*** (0.0066)	0.0682*** (0.0076)	0.0682*** (0.0076)	0.0682*** (0.0076)	0.0682*** (0.0076)	0.0646*** (0.0083)
Observations	1,500	1,500	1,500	1,500	1,500	1,500	1,500	1,500	1,500	1,500	1,500
Untreated	1,066	1,066	1,066	1,066	1,066	1,066	1,066	1,066	1,066	1,066	1,066
Treated	434	434	434	434	434	434	434	434	434	434	434
Matching Quality											
Pseudo-R2	0.002	0.003	0.003	0.004	0.004	0.011	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.004
Rosenbaum bounds sensitivity test	1.7	2.25	2.5	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
Standardized bias (p-value)	0.783	0.551	0.611	0.453	0.386	0.023	0.783	0.783	0.783	0.783	0.445

Bootstrapped standard errors based on 50 replications in brackets. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

Table B4 – Robustness: using entropy balancing and Diff-in-Diff estimations

<i>Panel A: Testing both DNS objectives</i>				
	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]
VARIABLES	Total external debt stocks in % of GDP	Total external debt stocks in % of GDP	Forest land biocapacity per capita	Forest land biocapacity per capita
DNS adoption	-0.3665*** (0.0795)	-0.3024*** (0.0700)	0.1139*** (0.0405)	0.0784* (0.0413)
Constant	2.5943*** (0.1071)	0.6009 (1.3034)	0.7062*** (0.1479)	-5.8016*** (2.0361)
Covariates	No	Yes	No	Yes
Country/FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year/FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	1,620	1,620	1,118	1,118
R-squared	0.6833	0.7383	0.9988	0.9988
<i>Panel B: Diff-in-Diff estimations</i>				
	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]
	drimp	ipw	stdipw	rc1
ATT: DNS adoption	0.0432*** (0.0148)	0.0895*** (0.0329)	0.0554*** (0.0193)	0.0432*** (0.0148)
Covariates	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	1,025	1,025	1,025	1,025

Note: in column [1] of Panel B, we present the doubly robust DiD estimator based on inverse probability of tilting and weighted least squares (drimp) (see [Sant’Anna and Zhao, 2020](#)). In column [2], we report the results of the inverse probability weighted DiD estimator (ipw) (see [Abadie, 2005](#)). In column [3], we report the results of the inverse probability weighting DiD estimator with stabilized weights (stdipw). Finally, we use the combination with the methods (drimp) and (dripw) in column [4]. Robust standard errors in parentheses *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.

Table B5 – Robustness-using endogenous switching regression model: Conditional expectations, treatment and heterogeneity effects

	Decision stage		Treatments effects
	DNS adopters	DNS non-adopters	
DNS adopters	(a) 0.1654*** (0.0035)	(c) -0.0581*** (0.0051)	TT = 0.1073*** (0.0001)
DNS non-adopters	(d) 0.1220*** (0.0032)	(b) -0.1044*** (0.0086)	TU = 0.0176*** (0.0002)
Heterogeneity effects	BH1 = 0.0463*** (0.0037)	BH0 = 0.0434*** (0.0049)	TH = 0.0029*** (0.0001)

Note: *** significant at 1%; Values in parentheses are standard errors. TT: Effect of the treatment on the treated; TU: Effect of the treatment on the untreated; BH1: Base heterogeneity effect for adopters; BH0: Base heterogeneity effect for non-adopters; TH: Transitional heterogeneity effect.

Figure 2: Robustness: using endogenous switching regression

Table B6 – Robustness-using systems GMM and cross-sectional estimations

VARIABLES	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]
	<i>Systems GMM</i>	<i>IV-2SLS</i>	<i>Cross-sectional</i>	<i>Cross-sectional</i>
Lag.Dependent variable	0.9775*** (0.0029)			
DNS adoption	0.0152*** (0.0028)	0.1243*** (0.0398)	0.0033* (0.0020)	0.0037* (0.0019)
Lag GDP per capita (log)	0.0135*** (0.0013)	0.0991*** (0.0107)	0.1299*** (0.0378)	0.1293*** (0.0381)
Lag debt service total	0.0024*** (0.0001)	-0.0039*** (0.0013)	-0.0077 (0.0055)	-0.0077 (0.0055)
lag climatic vulnerability score	0.2331*** (0.0198)	-1.3034*** (0.1187)	-1.3836*** (0.4111)	-1.3829*** (0.4042)
Property rights	0.0002*** (0.0000)	0.0010** (0.0004)	0.0002 (0.0017)	0.0002 (0.0017)
Democracy polity	-0.0001 (0.0003)	0.0023* (0.0013)	0.0049 (0.0044)	0.0044 (0.0045)
Constant	0.0030 (0.0214)	-0.7190*** (0.1175)	-0.9792* (0.4946)	-0.9762* (0.4934)
AR (2) test	0.011			
AR (1) test	0.801			
Sargan C-test/Kleibergen-Paap LM test, p-value	0.000	0.0000		
Hansen J-test	0.488	0.8892		
Number of instruments	72	2		
Observations	1,491	1,158	75	75
R-squared		0.6734	0.7571	0.7589
Number of country	74	127		

Note: we use the lag of the control variables as an internal instrument for the GMM systems, while the deforestation rate and the commitment to the environmental convention were used as external instruments for the IV-2SLS. Standard errors in parentheses *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table B7 – Heterogeneity: effects by type of DNS adoption

VARIABLES	[1]	[2]
Bilateral DNS	0.2368*** (0.0374)	
Multi-party DNS		0.0243*** (0.0073)
Constant	-0.6615*** (0.2186)	-0.6935*** (0.2171)
Covariates	Yes	Yes
Country/FE	Yes	Yes
Year/FE	Yes	Yes
Observations	1,477	1,477
R-squared	0.9240	0.9244

Robust standard errors in parentheses *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table B8 – Heterogeneity: dynamic effects

VARIABLES	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]
DNS adoption (t0)	0.0105** (0.0138)					
DNS adoption (t+1)		0.0120* (0.0151)				
DNS adoption (t+2)			0.0096*** (0.0181)			
DNS adoption (t+3)				0.0102*** (0.0165)		
DNS adoption (t+4)					0.0866*** (0.0163)	
DNS adoption (t+5)						0.0866*** (0.0163)
Constant	-0.5592*** (0.2143)	-0.5592*** (0.2143)	-0.6351*** (0.2220)	-0.6934*** (0.2130)	-0.4603** (0.1955)	-0.5104*** (0.1960)
Covariates	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country/FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year/FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	1,500	1,500	1,500	1,426	1,352	1,280
R-squared	0.9253	0.9253	0.9239	0.9315	0.9378	0.9443

Robust standard errors in parentheses *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table B9 – Heterogeneity: the role of structural factors

VARIABLES	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]	[7]	[8]	[9]	[10]
Emerging countries	Low income countries	High climate change vulnerability	Low climate change vulnerability	High control of corruption	Low control of corruption	High democracy	Low democracy	High fiscal discipline	Low fiscal discipline	
DNS adoption	0.0258** (0.0106)	0.0495*** (0.0082)	0.0489*** (0.0128)	-0.0703*** (0.0162)	0.0895*** (0.0178)	0.0394** (0.0196)	0.0470*** (0.0156)	0.0377*** (0.0098)	0.1640*** (0.0345)	0.0241** (0.0104)
Constant	-2.1927*** (0.3451)	-0.2551 (0.3403)	-2.0761*** (0.4775)	0.2637 (0.2325)	-0.3452 (0.2236)	-0.1106 (0.5956)	-2.4160*** (0.5996)	-0.0478 (0.1933)	-0.2747 (0.2456)	-0.7195** (0.3343)
Covariates	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country/FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year/FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	348	404	794	706	1,297	203	363	1,137	681	819
R-squared	0.9595	0.8570	0.9432	0.8318	0.9234	0.9454	0.9665	0.9424	0.9520	0.9477
[11]	[12]	[13]	[14]	[15]	[16]	[17]	[18]	[19]	[20]	
Loose fiscal stance	Strong fiscal stance	High policy protection of forest	low policy protection of forest	EITI countries	non-EITI countries	High engagement in environmental conventions	low engagement in environmental conventions	Phase of the business cycle bad times	Phase of the business cycle good times	
DNS adoption	0.0381*** (0.0089)	0.1600*** (0.0302)	0.0742*** (0.0139)	0.0650*** (0.0136)	0.0479*** (0.0181)	0.1428*** (0.0211)	0.0436*** (0.0086)	0.1136*** (0.0392)	0.0598*** (0.0126)	
Constant	0.2504 (0.1852)	-1.8466*** (0.4676)	-0.8550*** (0.2323)	-0.2854 (0.5375)	-0.8100*** (0.2244)	-1.5420*** (0.4033)	0.4988** (0.2360)	-2.2470*** (0.6329)	-0.3794 (0.2489)	
Covariates	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Country/FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Year/FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Observations	881	619	1,240	334	1,166	750	750	265	1,235	
R-squared	0.9416	0.9388	0.9242	0.9716	0.9329	0.9152	0.9366	0.9650	0.9318	

Robust standard errors in parentheses *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1